

iPLUG

Deliverable D4.1

Report on system modelling, simulation and advanced controllers for enhanced functionalities and services provision from multiport converters

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

AC	Alternate Current
B2B	Back to Back
DC	Direct Current
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DG	Distributed Generator
DN	Distribution Network
DSO	Distribution System Operators
FTR	Fault ride through
GFOL	Grid following
GFOR	Grid forming
LV	Low Voltage
MPC	Multiport Converter
MV	Medium Voltage
NMPZ	Non-minimum phase zero
OF	Objective Function
OPF	Optimal Power Flow
PCC	Point of Common Coupling
PLL	Phase Locked Loop
PV	Photovoltaic
RMS	Root Mean Square
SCR	Short Circuit Ratio
SM	Smart Meter
SOP	Soft Open Point
TAB	Triple Active Bridge

UC	Use Case
VDI	Voltage Deviation Index
VOC	Virtual Oscillator Control
VSC	Voltage Source Converter
VZT	Virtual Impedance Transient
ZOH	Zero Order Hold

Symbols

δ	Voltage angle
Ω_i	Set of buses adjacent to bus i
Π_m	Set of ports of MPC m
ρ	Index of MPC ports
θ_{ij}	Impedance angle of line $i - j$
E_{loss}	Grid energy losses
i	Current (Sec. 3), Index of grid bus (Sec. 5)
I_{ij}	Current flowing through the line $i - j$
j	Index of grid bus
m	Index of MPC in the grid
M_{MPC}	Number of MPCs in the grid
N	Transformer turns ratio (Sec. 3), Number of buses in the grid (Sec. 5)
$N_{\text{ports},m}$	Number of ports of MPC m
N_{tot}	Number of buses and MPCs in the grid
r_{ij}	Resistance of line $i - j$
S_{ij}	Complex power flow of line $i - j$
U	Generic voltage
V	Voltage magnitude
Z_{ij}	Impedance magnitude of line $i - j$

ω_n Angular grid frequency

C Capacitance

L Inductance

P Active power

Q Reactive power

R Resistance

t Time

1 Executive summary

This Deliverable illustrates the work carried out on operation and control of distribution grids with multiport converters (MPCs) in the context of iPLUG project.

MPCs are power electronics devices with multiple input and output ports, enabling the simultaneous interconnection of different distributed energy resources (DER) and grids.

The main objective of WP4 is to demonstrate the capability of integrating MPCs into the distribution grid seamlessly. This integration requires the development of grid models and average or reduced MPC more suitable for large-scale power system analysis.

The most suitable application of MPCs for grid operation and control is the Soft Open Point (SOP). SOPs are enhanced versions of traditional switches: in addition to grid re-configuration to enhance reliability, they allow precise control of active and reactive power setpoints at each port.

This deliverable focuses on SOPs, in particular MPC-enabled ones, i.e. SOPs whose DC-DC conversion stages are handled through MPCs. The introduction, in Chapter 2, reviews SOP applications in distribution grids and the role of MPCs in these applications.

The subsequent chapters follow the structure of WP4.

- Chapter 3 summarizes the work carried out in Task 4.1 on grid modelling and simulation. The chapter is divided into two case studies: one focusing on voltage analysis and voltage profile improvement through an MPC integrated into grid, and another on the evaluation of potential stability issues due to the grid integration of MPCs. Each case study presents the respective grid model, MPC average model, and lastly their integration for system-level studies.
- Chapter 4 describes the work associated with Task 4.2, mainly the development of local controllers for MPC-based SOPs, that ensure system stability and provide grid services. This chapter analyses both isolated and non-isolated MPCs. After a review of the main control strategies, a small-signal stability analysis is detailed for an isolated three-port soft open point (SOP) based on the triple active bridge. The modeling derivation is presented, and a sensitivity analysis is used to evaluate the impact of several control and grid parameters on the small-signal stability of the system. Furthermore, a control strategy is proposed for the operation of a three-port non-isolated SOP under abnormal grid conditions using both grid following and grid forming controls. Finally, a grid forming control implementation based on the unified voltage oscillator control concept is presented for MPCs together with a study on the impact of the grid conditions on grid forming control for distribution networks with different X/R ratios.
- Chapter, 5, reporting work from Task 4.3, focuses on centralized coordination through

high-level optimization studies. The optimal power flow (OPF) problem for optimizing the operation of MPC-based SOPs is formulated to improve grid performances. Two main objective functions are evaluated, mainly grid energy losses and voltage deviation minimization. Furthermore, the frequency support service provided by in MPC-interfaced microgrids is assessed based on a centralized model predictive control strategy.

2 Introduction

The increasing integration of distributed energy resources (DER) into distribution grids presents several technical challenges, including larger voltage deviations, thermal overloading of power lines, bidirectional power flows or increased congestion.

Traditional regulation mechanisms in distribution grids, such as on-load tap changers in transformers, were not designed for modern power systems that require continuous and faster actions, mainly due to the reduced predictability of energy generation from renewable energy sources and the resulting power flows [3].

To accommodate more DERs reliably, distribution system operators (DSOs) are often required to make substantial investments in network reinforcement and the replacement of aging infrastructure.

Among these devices, multiport converters (MPCs) play a pivotal role, particularly when deployed as enhanced soft open points (SOPs). SOPs are advanced power electronics devices that interconnect different AC feeders or buses within a distribution network, enabling greater operational flexibility.

MPC-based SOPs offer several advantages over traditional SOPs that rely on back-to-back voltage source converters (B2B VSCs). The key benefit lies in their multiport design, which allows them to connect multiple DERs and feeders simultaneously. For instance, a four-port MPC-based SOP could interlink two distribution grid feeders, a photovoltaic (PV) system, and an energy storage system. Through this configuration, SOPs provide continuous regulation of power flows, accurate control of active and reactive power, rapid current control that can mitigate short-circuit currents or improvement of unbalanced conditions. They also enable the interconnection of feeders operating at different voltage levels, that is otherwise complex with traditional switches [4].

The benefits of SOPs, as reviewed in [5], include reduced energy losses, minimized curtailment of renewable energy, improved reliability, deferred need for infrastructure reinforcement, improved energy arbitrage and voltage management. Moreover, employing MPCs as SOPs further enhances these benefits. The unified design of MPCs and their different topologies, including non-isolated, partially isolated, or fully isolated configurations

can adapt to different grids, conditions and applications. These designs may incorporate multi-transformer or multi-winding isolation, and a wide range of control strategies that can improve the decoupling between the ports, enhancing their performance as they offer services to the grid [6].

To operate MPC-based SOPs correctly, they must be accurately modelled. In the model, the level of detail of the grid can significantly affect the outcome of simulations and the resulting accuracy. Furthermore, their controls must be designed for specific applications, and stability analysis is required to guarantee system stability. On a system-wide level, the active and reactive power working conditions at each port and for each MPC in the system must be set in order to obtain specific benefits for the grid. Finally, global decentralized controls, such as model predictive controllers, can be designed for coordinating actions of different MPCs.

The present Deliverable covers all of these aspects, providing a complete overview on the operation and control of MPCs for distribution grids.

3 Grid modelling and simulation

This chapter describes the work carried out in Task 4.1, for the modelling and simulation of distribution grids integrated with MPCs, working mainly as SOPs. The work was divided into two parallel streams: in the first, a real LV grid from Catalonia region, as defined in WP1, is modelled to evaluate how a triple active bridge (TAB) based SOP can benefit the grid, specifically in improving its voltage profile and integrating more DERs. In the second work stream, the IEEE 33 bus system is modelled to evaluate how the design of multiport converts affects grid's small-signal stability.

Each of the work streams involves three main steps:

- Power grid modelling for steady-state and stability analysis.
- Average modelling of MPCs, to reduce the computational burden of switching models and allow large-scale power system studies.
- Integration of MPC models into power grid models, followed by steady-state and dynamic analysis.

The following sections illustrate each of these steps for both the voltage analysis after the MPC integration in the Anell LV grid and the stability analysis of MPC integrated into the IEEE 33 bus system.

3.1 Case study 1: Voltage analysis of distribution grids with integrated MPCs

This section presents the modeling of a real distribution grid used to evaluate the performance of an MPC in connecting two low-voltage grids at different voltage levels, along with a DER at the third port.

The grid data is provided by Anell, a distribution system operator (DSO) based in Catalonia. The reference Use Case is UC 1.2, described in the Deliverable D1.1. The actual implementation of the UC 1.2 has undergone slight changes: the MPC employed has three-ports instead of four. It works as a SOP connecting two low voltage grids at different voltage levels and a DER, for example a 100 kW PV plant, at the third DC port, as shown in the scheme in Fig. 1. This change is consistent with the work carried out in WP2 and described in the Deliverable D2.1, that focused on the Triple Active Bridge (TAB).

Figure 1: Anell LV grid Use Case

The flowchart of the grid modelling process is shown in Fig. 2. It requires, on one hand, grid topological data including physical characteristics of the lines and the position of the nodes. On the other, it requires data from smart meters, to understand the distribution of the loads through the power grid.

Figure 2: Grid modelling flowchart.

Starting with the grid topology, Fig. 3 shows the actual georeferenced grids considered in this use case. The purple grid operates at a nominal voltage of 400 V, while the green grid operates at 230 V.

The data provided by Anell to model the grid are:

- The list of lines, specifying the pair of nodes they connect.

- The resistance and reactance values per meter, for each line.
- The total length of each line.

Figure 3: Anell LV grid Use Case

The complete grid topology obtained from the available data is shown in Fig. 4. Both grids exhibit a radial structure, with the transformers being the uppermost elements, and the loads being the lowest ones.

In the figure, the two larger squares (bus 62662 and 63590) represent the transformers connecting the LV grids to the MV distribution grid. These are the main sources (slack buses) of the modelled grids. The little squares represent the main distribution boxes of the LV grid, that gather lines connected to the interconnection and load buses. Interconnection nodes are represented as small circles and loads as stars.

The number of buses, distribution boxes, loads and interconnection nodes are shown in Table 1.

	230 V grid	400 V grid
N. buses	57	78
N. dist. boxes	7	13
N. loads	24	36
N. interconn.	26	29

Table 1: Summary of Anell’s grid buses.

Considering the large amount of buses in the system and the computational burden added by measurement blocks for each bus in Simulink, we assume to be monitoring mainly the distribution box nodes, listed in Table 2. The list will be useful for easily identifying the key nodes in the grid while reading voltage profiles plots in the case study section.

The position of the MPC and the corresponding PV plant is between bus 63692 (400 V grid) and 63784 (230 V grid).

Once the grid topology is defined, the load profiles and distribution are required as inputs for the initial power flow analysis.

Figure 4: Complete topology of Anell LV grids. MPC ports connections are highlighted by red circles.

230 V dist. boxes	400 V dist. boxes	
63085	63409	63511
63922	63334	63295
63784	63197	63072
63725	62914	63056
63777	63140	63263
63853	63343	63461
97508	63692	

Table 2: List of the main nodes (distribution boxes) for both LV grids.

The data on active and reactive power absorbed (or injected, when DER are present) are measured through smart meters in the load buses, corresponding mostly to residential loads. Each load bus in the grid is associated to one or more smart meters.

This is shown in Fig. 5a. For example, in the figure, smart meters (SM) 4 and 5 both refer to load bus 62980, and the corresponding load profiles are added together.

The load profiles are obtained from the SCADA data. Each smart meter is characterized by a unique identifier (ID-SCADA) and the recorded data include hourly active and reactive power imported or exported in kW and kVAr, as in Fig. 5b, shown for SM 5 with ID 119491.

The grids are finally modelled in Simulink, Fig. 6.

Before carrying out power flow and time domain simulation analyses, the computational burden of the Simulink model is reduced. The series line impedances are replaced by their equivalents, the open circuit branches that were not ending in load buses are removed, and the measurement blocks are limited to the distribution boxes only.

With the Simulink model ready, an initial steady-state power flow study was carried out

Smart meters	Node Name	Acometida	ID-SCADA
SM_1	97510	48748	138479
SM_2	62954	45465	71656
SM_3	62952	45466	83751
SM_4	62980	45464	119491
SM_5	62980	45464	72693
SM_6	62899	45463	95337

numserie	dataLectura	activaImport	activaExport	r1	r2	r3	r4
119491	2023-04-01T01:00:00	0.32	0	0.11	0	0	0
119491	2023-04-01T02:00:00	0.24	0	0.08	0	0	0.01
119491	2023-04-01T03:00:00	0.15	0	0	0	0	0.06
119491	2023-04-01T04:00:00	0.15	0	0.01	0	0	0.05
119491	2023-04-01T05:00:00	0.12	0	0	0	0	0.08

(a) Nodes to smart meters matching

(b) Smart meters data

Figure 5: Real load data from Anell grid

Figure 6: Simulink model of Anell grid. The purple block corresponds to the 400 V grid, the green block to the 230 V grid and the red block to the MPC position.

in order to check the convergence of the system of non-linear equations characterizing the system and to evaluate the equilibrium point of the grids, set as the initial state before the introduction of the MPC.

This initial scenario does not show a particular impact of voltage profiles, mainly due to the grids being in a lowly loaded rural area.

In order to consider a more realistic voltage profile of a common urban LV grid, or assuming a strong electrification of the rural area considered, a uniform load multiplication factor is applied. This keeps the load spatial distribution and profiles, while providing a more interesting use case to analyse.

With this change, the results of the power flow analysis for the independent grids, in terms of voltage profiles of the distribution boxes, are shown in Fig. 7. The figures show

the typical voltage profiles of healthy radial grids, with voltage deviations between 1% and 2% of the nominal value.

Figure 7: Voltage profiles of Anell LV grids obtained from the load flow analysis

These results represent the benchmark for the analysis of the impact of the MPC installation, together with a flexible DER, in the power grid.

3.2 MPC models

Several multiport converter topologies have been explored throughout the development of the iPLUG project. These topologies were classified in terms of galvanic isolation and other characteristics in deliverable D1.1. In this deliverable, some of these topologies are modeled and integrated into grid models for dynamic and static grid studies.

An isolated topology is first considered to detail the model of it. The topology is based on the triple active bridge, a three-port isolated DC-DC converter whose operation and control are based on its predecessor, the well-known dual active bridge converter. The triple active bridge connects two AC grids and one DC system (source or load), forming an enhanced soft open point, as shown in Figure 8. The AC grids could be AC linked or not, i.e. part of the same distribution network, or isolated distribution networks.

3.2.1 Multiport converter description

This section describes the multiport converter under study and the main operation considerations.

The soft open point is a power electronics solution that aims to replace or enhance the operation of normally open points in distribution networks. The typical configuration is based on the Back-to-Back topology which interconnects two different feeders as a nor-

Figure 8: Grid-connected multiport converter based on the triple active bridge

mally open point would do [3]. Furthermore, the soft open point can provide grid services that the normally open point cannot. This is thanks to the control capabilities of power electronics used in soft open points which enhance the controllability, flexibility, and reliability of the distribution networks. Isolated multiport converters, such as the triple active bridge, can enhance soft open points safety, voltage adaptation, and integration and sharing of distributed energy resources among multiple feeders of the AC distribution network, as discussed in [6].

Figure 8 shows the enhanced soft open point based on the triple active bridge. In this Deliverable, it is considered that two out of the three ports are connected to two different AC grids represented by the Thevenin equivalents in the point of common coupling. Furthermore, the third port is connected to a DC energy resource represented by a controlled current source. The soft open point topology is realized by using two 2-level inverters connected to the feeders, and the triple active bridge fully isolates the three ports in the soft open point.

The control mode of the topology is such that inverters 1 and 2 are controlled in VdcQ and PQ control modes, respectively. In both cases, the control is realized in the dq synchronous reference frame as depicted in Figure 8. Furthermore, the isolated DC-DC triple active bridge is in charge of v_{dc2} and v_{dc3} regulation, and its control is implemented through two PI controllers, one for each output port (ports 2 and 3) as in [7].

To obtain a multiport converter model, the models of the inverter and the triple active bridge are derived separately and then interconnected. Thus, the complete model is realized by interconnecting the two inverters and triple active bridge models respecting the control modes described above.

3.2.2 Inverter model

In this subsection, the derivation of the dynamic model of the inverter is detailed.

As mentioned above, 2-level inverters are considered for low-voltage AC interconnec-

Figure 9: 2-Level inverter with LCL filter circuit

tion, which are commonly accompanied by a filtering stage. The last is implemented by means of an L or LCL filter modeled based on the circuit depicted in Figure 9. The Kirchoff voltage and current laws are applied and equations (1)-(3) are derived for the LCL filter case. In case of using L filters, v_f can be replaced by v_{PCC} in (1), while (2) and (3) are omitted. The LCL filter is considered for the remainder of this section.

$$\frac{di_{inv}}{dt} = \frac{v_{inv} - v_f - i_{inv}R_f}{L_f} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{di_g}{dt} = \frac{v_f - v_{pcc} - i_gR_{fg}}{L_{fg}} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dv_f}{dt} = \frac{i_{inv} - i_g}{C_f} \quad (3)$$

where i_{inv} and i_g are the currents in the inverter and the grid, i_{inv} , v_f and v_{PCC} are the voltages the inverter, the filter capacitor, and the point of common coupling (PCC), L_f and L_{fg} are the inductances on the inverter and grid side of the filter, C_f is the capacitance of the filter, and R_f and R_{fg} are the parasitic resistances of the filter inductors (omitted in the Figure 9 for simplicity).

Since the model is derived and implemented in the synchronous reference frame, equations (1)-(3) change and are rewritten in (4)-(6).

$$\frac{di_{inv}^{dq}}{dt} = \frac{v_{inv}^{dq} - v_f^{dq} - i_{inv}^{dq}R_f}{L_f} + j\omega_n i_{inv}^{dq} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{di_g^{dq}}{dt} = \frac{v_f^{dq} - v_{pcc}^{dq} - i_g^{dq}R_{fg}}{L_{fg}} + j\omega_n i_g^{dq} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dv_f^{dq}}{dt} = \frac{i_{inv}^{dq} - i_g^{dq}}{C_f} + j\omega_n v_f^{dq} \quad (6)$$

where superscript d and q refer to the direct and quadrature axis in the synchronous reference frame, and ω_n is the nominal angular frequency of the grid.

The voltage at the inverter output v_{inv}^{dq} depends on the control strategy implemented in the inverter, which could have many variations. Here, the grid-following strategy is

detailed, which results in different expressions for v_{inv}^{dq} depending on the control model used.

One can start by deriving an expression for the inverter dq voltage references from the block diagram shown in Figure 10 which depicts the cascaded control structure based on linear PI controllers. By inspecting the resulting expression (7), it is evident that v_{inv}^{dq*} is the output control action of the AC current controller, which is the inner control loop in the cascaded control implementation. The references for the last (i_g^{dq*}) depend on the outer control loop, which could be implemented in active and reactive power (PQ) control mode or DC-link voltage and reactive power (VdcQ) control mode. The only difference between these two control modes is the definition of the d-axis current reference i_g^{d*} presented in (8) and (9). The q-axis current reference i_g^{q*} remains the same for both control modes and is expressed in (10).

$$v_{inv}^{dq*} = (i_g^{dq*} - i_g^{dq})(k_p^i + \frac{k_i^i}{s}) \quad (7)$$

$$i_g^{d*} = (v_{dc}^* - v_{dc})(k_p^{dc} + \frac{k_i^{dc}}{s}) \quad (8)$$

$$i_g^{d*} = (P_{inv}^* - P_{inv})(k_p^P + \frac{k_i^P}{s}) \quad (9)$$

$$i_g^{q*} = (Q_{inv}^* - Q_{inv})(k_p^Q + \frac{k_i^Q}{s}) \quad (10)$$

where v_{inv}^{dq*} , i_g^{d*} , and i_g^{q*} are the dq inverter voltage and grid current references, v_{inv}^{dq} , i_g^d , and i_g^q the dq inverter voltage and grid current measurements, P_{inv}^* and Q_{inv}^* are the inverter active and reactive power references, P and Q the inverter active and reactive power measurements, and k_p^i , k_i^i , k_p^Q , k_i^Q , k_p^P , and k_i^P are the proportional and integral gains of the active power, reactive power, and dq grid current controllers.

Considering the inputs for the grid-following controllers, the active and reactive power, DC-link voltage, and AC current measurements are needed. Also, considering the definition of grid-following control, the inverter should implement a grid synchronization method that guarantees that the injected currents correspond to the power required. The phase-locked loop (PLL) depicted in Figure 11 is considered. The PLL model is derived and presented in (11) and (12).

$$\omega_{pll} = (0 - v_{pcc}^q)(k_p^{pll} + \frac{k_i^{pll}}{s}) \quad (11)$$

$$\theta_{pll} = \frac{\omega_{pll}}{s} \quad (12)$$

Figure 10: Grid following block diagram

Figure 11: PLL block diagram

where ω_{pll} and θ_{pll} are the angular frequency and phase angle of the measured v_{PCC} , respectively, and k_p^{pll} and k_i^{pll} are the proportional and integral gains of the PLL controller.

3.2.3 Triple active bridge model

In this subsection, the derivation of the dynamic model of the triple active bridge is detailed.

The triple active bridge converter is an isolated DC-DC multiport converter and its operation was detailed in the Deliverable D2.1 of iPLUG project. Also, the full-order and reduced-order models of the converter were derived, with one linear and a non-linear controller designed and tested in simulation. Since the objective of the models derived in this deliverable is to integrate them into grid models, the computational burden needs to be considered. Therefore, a reduced-order model is considered and its derivation is summarized next.

The reduced-order model of the triple active bridge ignores the fast dynamic of the high-frequency transformer currents. Therefore, the AC currents flowing through the active bridge inductors are not considered in the model. Hence, the triple active bridge model is derived based on the power flow equations as in [8]. Assuming that the converter operates using single phase-shift modulation and that the duty cycle at each of the full bridges is constant and equal to 50%, the power flow equations can be written as in (13) and (14) [8]. Furthermore, the dynamic equations for the voltages at each port can be derived considering the power balance on the capacitor. Equations (15) to (17) define the dynamic model of the triple active bridge converter. A graphical representation of the triple active bridge circuit and its average reduced-order models is presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Triple active bridge model

$$P_{i,j}^{tab} = \frac{n_{i,j} v_{dc_i} d_{c_j} d_{i,j} (1 - |d_{i,j}|)}{2 f_{sw} L_{i,j}}, \forall i, j \in [1, 2, 3] \wedge i \neq j. \quad (13)$$

$$i_{i,j}^{tab} = \frac{n_{i,j} v_{dc_i} d_{i,j} (1 - |d_{i,j}|)}{2 f_{sw} L_{i,j}}, \forall i, j \in [1, 2, 3] \wedge i \neq j. \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{dv_{dc_1}}{dt} = \frac{P_1 - P_{1,2} - P_{1,3}}{V_1 C_1} = \frac{i_1 - i_{1,2} - i_{1,3}}{C_1} \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{dv_{dc_2}}{dt} = \frac{P_{1,2} - P_{2,3} - P_2}{V_2 C_2} = \frac{i_{1,2} - i_{2,3} - i_2}{C_2} \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{dv_{dc_3}}{dt} = \frac{P_{1,3} + P_{2,3} - P_3}{V_3 C_3} = \frac{i_{1,3} + i_{2,3} - i_3}{C_3} \quad (17)$$

where $P_{i,j}$ and $i_{i,j}$ are the active power and current flowing from port i to port j , $d_{i,j}$ is the normalized phase-shift between ports i and j , $n_{i,j}$ is the turns ratio between port windings in the high-frequency transformer, v_i and v_j are the voltages at ports i and j , f_{sw} is the switching frequency of the active bridges, $L_{i,j}$ are the equivalent inductances between ports i and j , and C_i is the capacitance at port i .

Considering the models developed in previous subsections and the multiport converter depicted in Figure 8, the dynamic model for the multiport converter is implemented in Simulink using infinite bus for both AC grids and is presented in Figure 13. The grid model should be later replaced here, and the states initialized to run time domain simulations as it will be described in the next subsection.

3.3 MPC integration

In this section, a procedure for integrating the multiport converter model into grid models in Simulink is presented. The methodology presented here is detailed using a Thevenin equivalent for both AC grids but is valid for any grid model.

Figure 13: Grid following block diagram

3.3.1 Operation point definition

First, the operation point of each port should be defined. Since the multiport converter is integrated into AC grids, only AC ports are considered in this stage. Hence, for each AC port, the active and reactive power references should be first defined. These references should comply with power balance and sizing of the multiport converter as described in (18) and (19). This operation point could come from a higher layer controller, which will be detailed in chapter 5.

$$P_1^{tab} + P_2^{tab} + P_3^{tab} = 0 \tag{18}$$

$$P_i^{tab} \leq P_{i,max}^{tab} \quad \forall i \in [1, 2, 3] \tag{19}$$

3.3.2 MPC steady-state model integration

Once the operation point is defined, a steady-state representation of the multiport converter can be integrated to the grid model. For this, the multiport converter connection to each grid is represented in Simulink as an ideal voltage source as shown in Figure 14. Then, the load flow analyzer from Simulink/Simscape is used to initialize the amplitude and phase angle grid voltages, including the ideal voltage sources representing the multiport connection.

3.3.3 MPC dynamic model integration

Then, with the steady-state model of the grid and multiport converters initialized, the dynamic model can be integrated considering the steady-state measurements from the above subsection for the initialization of the dynamic states (currents and voltages). Once the dynamic states are initialized, an ideal three-phase switch is used to smoothly shift

Figure 14: Steady-state representation of a multiport converter using an Ideal Voltage Source in Simulink.

Figure 15: From steady-state to dynamic multiport converter models integration to grid models in Simulink

from the ideal voltage source model to the dynamic multiport converter model smoothly, see Figure 15b. Figure 16 shows the transition from the steady state model to the dynamic model for four state variables: active power in grid 2 (upper left), DC voltage of grid 1 inverter (upper right), d-axis current of grid 1 inverter (bottom left), q-axis current grid 1 inverter (bottom right).

3.4 Grid integration of MPCs (voltage analysis)

The Anell LV grid model was described in Section 3, the MPC models for grid studies in Section 3.2, and their integration in Section 3.3.3. This section completes the description of the work carried out in Task 4.1, by evaluating the integration of a TAB-based SOP in the Anell power, as defined in Section 3, Fig. 1.

The main objective is to evaluate the benefits of installing DERs in the grid and connecting grids at different voltage levels through an MPC.

The number of the MPC ports is assigned as follows:

- Port 1: connection to the 230 V grid, through bus 63784.
- Port 2: connection to the 400 V grid, through bus 63692.
- Port 3: connection to the PV plant, assumed to provide 100 kW as maximum power.

Figure 16: Simulation of the transition from steady state representation to dynamic model of the multiport converter.

The MPC losses are assumed to be negligible compared to grid losses, and the active power balance between the ports of the MPC holds at any time, resulting in

$$P_1 + P_2 = P_3 \tag{20}$$

The ports are sized for a maximum apparent power of 100 kVA.

Active power transfer The initial evaluation is based on steady-state studies: power flow analyses are carried out for different values of active and reactive power setpoints in each port of the TAB-based SOP. For the steady-state analysis, it is assumed that P and Q setpoints are perfectly followed by the MPC controllers in each port. The status of both grids for different P-Q setpoints is assessed through the voltage magnitude deviations of the main buses (distribution boxes, defined in Table 2). For the initial scenario, Q_1 and Q_2 are set to zero. The reactive power compensation and its effect on voltage profiles will be analysed in the next scenario.

Fig. 17 shows the voltage deviations of 230 V grid’s buses, for different active power setpoints in port 1, P_1 . Similarly, Fig. 18 refers to the 400 V grid and active power setpoints in port 2, P_2 .

Voltage deviations are plotted as a function of each port’s active power output (positive values) or input (negative values).

For instance, $P_3 = 100$ kW of active power from the PV plant in port 3 can be transferred totally to the 230 V grid through the port 1 ($P_1 = 100$ kW), to the 400 V grid through the port 2 ($P_2 = 100$ kW), or to both grids (for example $P_1 = 60$ kW and $P_2 = 40$ kW). The

Figure 17: Voltage deviations of 230 V grid buses for different active power setpoints in port 1 P_1 . The bus connected to the MPC is highlighted in red.

first two cases, used as a benchmark, are equivalent to having the PV plant connected to only one grid at a time through an inverter, without the MPC. Conversely, negative power corresponds to power transfer from one port to another. The case with $P_2 = -50$ kW and $P_3 = 30$ kW corresponds to the power transfer of $P_1 = 80$ kW from the 400 V grid and the PV plant to the 230 V grid.

From Figs. 17 and 18, it is clear that the presence of the MPC, connecting the PV plant to both power grids, mitigates the voltage deviations by distributing the impact of the new resource across the two grids.

The 230 V grid experiences a maximum voltage increase of 5% when the PV power is transferred completely to it through the port 1, which is equivalent to a scenario without a MPC. However, by employing both MPC ports and reducing the power transferred to port 1, while increasing the power transfer to port 2, can significantly enhance the voltage deviation of the 230 V grid. Moving to the negative values, the power transfer (e.g. $P_1 = -100$ kW) from port 1 (230 V grid) to port 2 (400 V grid) leads to very large voltage deviations, with a minimum of -10%, and should be avoided.

The 400 V grid exhibits lower voltage deviations (up to 1% when the whole PV power is transferred to port 2). Transferring power from the 400 V grid to the 230 V grid, up to $P_2 = -100$ kW, can be considered acceptable, as the voltage deviations fall below 5%.

It is worth noting that the presence of the MPC and the PV plant integration affects mostly the voltage deviations of the feeder where they are installed. Indeed, the voltage deviations in the other feeders are limited to values below 3%. This depends both on the radial topology of the grid and the location of the MPC, close to the end of the feeder.

Figure 18: Voltage deviations of 400 V grid buses for different active power setpoints in port 2 P_2 . The bus connected to the MPC is highlighted in red.

Reactive power compensation The P-Q setpoints of MPC ports can be adjusted in order to further improve voltage deviations in both grids.

In this scenario, the effect of reactive power compensation in each port of the MPC is assessed, given a fixed active power transfer of $P_i = 95$ kW. Considering a MPC sized for $S_{max} = 100$ kVA, the reactive power available corresponds to approximately $Q_i = 30$ kVAr.

Fig. 19 shows the impact of reactive power compensation on the 230 V. According to the results, the reactive power compensation improves the voltage deviations from a maximum of 5% to 2%. Similar results are obtained for the 400 V grid.

Figure 19: Voltage deviations of 230 V grid buses for different reactive power setpoints in port 1 Q_1 .

If the MPCs are employed to provide reactive power compensation and reduce the volt-

age deviations in the grid they are integrated into, their ports can be sized to handle larger reactive power values.

For example, for the scenario under analysis, the full power from the PV plant can be transferred to the grid without curtailment by increasing the maximum apparent power of the MPC by approximately 10%. This is equivalent to allow $P_i = 100$ kW and $Q_i = 50$ kVAR maximum.

Fig. 20 shows the voltage deviations achieved in this case, that reach values less than 1%. This leads to the PV plant installation having minimal impact in the grid and increasing its hosting capacity, as additional renewable energy sources can be installed without affecting the grid's reliable operation.

Figure 20: Voltage deviations of 230 V grid buses for different reactive power setpoints in port 1 Q_1 , MPC ports oversized.

3.5 Case study 2: Stability analysis of distribution grids with integrated MPCs

The grid models used in iPlug consider distribution networks, so MV and LV levels with renewable integration are studied. The following components are modelled:

- Thevenin equivalent
- RL transmission lines
- Loads
- VSCs
- MPCs

In this section, all the elements are described in detail, except for MPCs that are explained in Section 3.6. Non-linear and linear models are derived. All the equilibrium points used to linearise the systems are obtained from a power flow calculation. In the cases without MPC, MATPOWER is used [9]. However, when the MPC is added, as DC power flow is required to consider the internal connection, MATA CDC is used. MATA CDC is an extension of MATPOWER, which calculates AC and DC power flows sequentially, as explained in [10].

3.5.1 Thevenin equivalent

The studied grids are initially radial, with a connection to a main grid, e.g. a connection to the transmission grid, which is defined as a Thevenin equivalent. In the case of the linear model, the system is defined in state space as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{i}_{TH}^q \\ \dot{i}_{TH}^d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-(R_{TH})}{L_{TH}} & -\omega \\ \omega & \frac{-R_{TH}}{L_{TH}} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_{TH}^q \\ i_{TH}^d \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-1}{L_{TH}} & 0 & \frac{1}{L_{TH}} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-1}{L_{TH}} & 0 & \frac{1}{L_{TH}} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} u_{TH}^q \\ u_{TH}^d \\ u_q^{net} \\ u_d^{net} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (21)$$

where the voltages defined as TH are related to the Thevenin equivalent and the components defined as net are related to the connection with the MV grid (after the RL). It should be noticed that the linear model is described in qd sequence, which facilitates the linearization, as the measurements will have a step form instead of a sinusoidal form. The output of this model is directly the Thevenin currents.

3.5.2 RL transmission lines

RL transmission lines are defined across the system to represent the cables in the grid. As their structure is an RL as in the case of the Thevenin equivalent, their state space representation has the same structure:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{i}_{RL}^q \\ \dot{i}_{RL}^d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-(R_{RL})}{L_{RL}} & -\omega \\ \omega & \frac{-R_{RL}}{L_{RL}} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_{RL}^q \\ i_{RL}^d \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-1}{L_{RL}} & 0 & \frac{1}{L_{RL}} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-1}{L_{RL}} & 0 & \frac{1}{L_{RL}} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} u_a^q \\ u_a^d \\ u_b^q \\ u_b^d \end{bmatrix}, \quad (22)$$

where a and b are the nodes between the RL. The output are the RL currents.

3.5.3 Loads

Loads are shunt devices, that is, they are connected between a given bus and the reference bus. They can be treated as constant impedance loads, which by definition are linear, and

power loads. In this deliverable, they are defined as constant impedance loads. Figure 21 depicts the model of the load.

Figure 21: Load model.

The state space of the loads is defined as four different state spaces, that are connected between them with the help of the *connect* command of Matlab. Hence, the first linear model defines the node:

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_{Load}^q \\ i_{Load}^d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_{generator}^q \\ u_{generator}^d \end{bmatrix}, \quad (23)$$

where i_{Load} defines the current that the load receives and $i_{generator}$ are the currents that came from the generators. It should be noted that the size of the matrix depends on the number of n generators that exist, so the size of the numerical matrix will always be $2n \cdot 2n$.

Inductor dynamics are defined as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{i}_{iLoad}^q \\ \dot{i}_{iLoad}^d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\omega \\ \omega & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_{iLoad}^q \\ i_{iLoad}^d \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{L_{Load}} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{L_{Load}} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} v_{NET}^q \\ v_{NET}^d \end{bmatrix}, \quad (24)$$

where i_{iLoad} is the current that flows through the inductor and v_{NET} is the voltage of the network. The output of this system is the currents of the inductor.

The third system calculates the resistor current from the currents of the load and the inductors as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_{rLoad}^q \\ i_{rLoad}^d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_{Load}^q \\ i_{Load}^d \\ i_{iLoad}^q \\ i_{iLoad}^d \end{bmatrix}, \quad (25)$$

The last state space used to define the loads is related to the resistor:

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{NET}^q \\ v_{NET}^d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_{Load} & 0 & irq0 \\ 0 & R_{Load} & ird0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_{rLoad}^q \\ i_{rLoad}^d \\ Rld_{NET} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (26)$$

where $irq0$ and $ird0$ are the equilibrium points of the current that flows through the load and Rld_{NET} defines a disturbance that could be applied at the nominal value of the load.

3.5.4 Voltage Source Converters

The VSCs defined in this project could operate in Grid-following (GFOL) or Grid-forming (GFOR) mode, hence their control structure differs in each case.

GFOL

In the case of the GFOL VSCs the electrical and control structures are as defined in Figure 22.

Figure 22: GFOL control of a VSC [1].

The complete linear model of all the control parts is explained in detail in [11]. As demonstrated in [11] a rotation has to be considered to define the Park transformations. Consequently, there are two frames: the global and the local frame, in which the electrical part and the control part are defined, respectively.

GFOR

The differences with the GFOL model are the droops used for the angle calculation and the q reference voltage and the voltage control. Hence, the control structure is defined in Figure 23.

The structure of the new controller elements is as with the droops and the current control of the GFOL model. Therefore, the linear model is obtained again as in [11].

3.6 MPC models

The MPC model used in the small-signal studies is a 2-ports SOP. A master-slave control configuration is defined, hence one port controls the active and reactive power, while the

Figure 23: GFOR control of a VSC.

other controls the DC voltage and reactive power. Both AC-DC ports are defined as VSCs, therefore their structure is as explained in Section 3.5.4. Additionally, it is required to add the DC line that interconnects both ports in the model. This connection has one capacitor to ensure the model's feasibility.

The linear model of the system has the same state space matrices as the VSCs but adds the DC components. Therefore, the DC current calculation and the DC line state spaces are defined.

DC current is calculated from the AC active power and the DC voltage such as:

$$i_{DC} = \frac{-P_{AC}}{V_{DC}} \quad (27)$$

Consequently, the state space is:

$$i_{DC} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-3v_{qc}^{c0}}{2V_{0DC}} & \frac{-3v_{dc}^{c0}}{2V_{0DC}} & \frac{-3i_{qs}^{c0}}{2V_{0DC}} & \frac{-3i_{ds}^{c0}}{2V_{0DC}} & \frac{3}{2} \cdot \frac{i_{qs}^{c0} \cdot v_{qc}^{c0} + i_{ds}^{c0} \cdot v_{dc}^{c0}}{V_{0DC}^2} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_c^{qs} \\ i_c^{ds} \\ v_c^{qc} \\ v_c^{dc} \\ V_{DC} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (28)$$

where i_c^s are the currents of the converter in the control frame and v_c^c are the voltages of the converter in the control frame. V_{DC} represents the DC voltage.

The DC line of the system is modelled as a PI line [12] considering the resistances and inductances near 0. The capacitors are defined as a function of the desired settling time, the base power and the DC voltage. The state space is obtained from the connectivity matrix.

3.7 Grid integration of MPCs (stability analysis)

The IEEE 33 buses system, Figure 24 is analyzed as a whole linear system. This study considers a scenario of a large amount of renewable generation. Therefore, bus number 1 is connected to a main AC grid, while the other generators are considered inverters connected to PV plants. Initially, these inverters are defined in Grid-following (GFOL) mode.

The control parameters are shown in Table 3.

/*

Therefore, first, the system is studied in stable conditions and without any MPCs. To check the validity of the linear model, a comparison is held between the linear and the non-linear models. Figure 25 shows the results when a variation of the 5% is applied to the load of bus 21.

The closed-loop eigenvalues obtained from the linear model are shown in the next fig-

Figure 24: IEEE 33 bus system [2].

Parameter	Value
τ_s	1e-3 s
τ_{PLL}	0.02 s
ξ_{PLL}	0.707
τ_P	0.1 s
τ_Q	0.1 s
τ_f	0.1 s
K_f	0.02
τ_u	0.1 s
K_u	0.02
τ_{md}	1e-5 s
τ_{cmd}	1.2e-4 s
τ_{ZOH}	1e-5 s

Table 3: Parameters of the VSCs.

Figure 25: VSC in bus 22 powers and frequency linear and non-linear results.

ures. It should be noticed that a line with 0.05 damping factor is represented. By this, it is checked if an eigenvalue is smaller than 0.05, thus it could be problematic for the dynamics of the system.

Figure 26: Eigenvalues initial case.

Figure 27: Zoom at eigenvalues initial case.

The results show that two eigenvalues exist with a damping factor smaller than 0.05 working at a frequency different than 50 Hz.

The participation factors, as shown in Figure 28, are related especially to the outer loop of the VSC of bus 18 and a small interaction also appears with the VSC of bus 33.

To study with more detail the IEEE 33 buses system, scenarios changing some variables of the inverters are presented in the following sections.

	NET.iq ₁₂	0.20	0.20
	NET.id ₁₂	0.16	0.16
	NET.id _{13,4}	0.19	0.19
	NET.iq _{16,7}	0.12	0.12
	GFOL1.Ke _p	1.00	1.00
	GFOL1.Ke _q	0.99	0.99
	GFOL1.cmdq ₂	0.84	0.84
States	GFOL1.is _q	0.19	0.19
	GFOL1.is _d	0.22	0.22
	GFOL1.ucap _q	0.55	0.55
	GFOL1.ucap _d	0.60	0.60
	GFOL4.Ke _p	0.23	0.23
	GFOL4.Ke _q	0.23	0.23
	GFOL4.cmdq ₂	0.20	0.20
	GFOL4.ucap _q	0.13	0.13
	GFOL4.ucap _d	0.14	0.14
		61	62
		Eigenvalues	

Figure 28: Participation factors with the critical eigenvalues.

3.7.1 GFOL converters parameters

Firstly, the time constant of the PI of the active power is increased and reduced. In these sensitivity analyses, only the critical eigenvalues are plotted, in Figure 29.

From the results, it can be concluded that if the time constant of the power outer loop is increased, the damping factor, and hence the dynamics, are improved. However, it has to be considered that slow dynamics of the outer loops may not accomplish the grid requirements.

If the reactive power time constant of the PI control is changed, the results are shown in Figure 30. Again, the dynamics are improved if the time constant of the reactive outer loop is increased. Furthermore, in Figure 31 the PLL time constant is modified to see the effects generated on the critical eigenvalues.

From the results, it can be seen that when the time constant of the PLL is very fast, instabilities appear. The participation factors of these eigenvalues are studied, as shown in Figure 32.

In all cases, each eigenvalue is related to the PLL of each converter, as the participation factors depend on the error of the angle and the d component of the voltage. The PLL has to be always slower than the inner current loop, which has a time constant of 1 ms. Therefore, it can be concluded that with the original parameters, the time constant of the PLL could never be less than 0.01 s.

In Figure 33 the gain of the voltage droop is also changed to see how much it affects

Figure 29: Eigenvalues obtained by changing the active power time constant.

Figure 30: Eigenvalues changing reactive power time constant.

Figure 31: Eigenvalues changing PLL time constant.

States	GFOL1.ud _m d	0.00	0.00	0.83	0.00
	GFOL1.ud _z oh1	0.00	0.00	0.13	0.00
	GFOL1.ud _z oh2	0.00	0.00	0.80	0.00
	GFOL1.etheta _x	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00
	GFOL2.ud _m d	0.83	0.00	0.00	0.00
	GFOL2.ud _z oh1	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.00
	GFOL2.ud _z oh2	0.81	0.00	0.00	0.00
	GFOL2.etheta _x	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	GFOL3.ud _m d	0.00	0.83	0.00	0.00
	GFOL3.ud _z oh1	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.00
	GFOL3.ud _z oh2	0.00	0.80	0.00	0.00
	GFOL3.etheta _x	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00
	GFOL4.ud _m d	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.83
	GFOL4.ud _z oh1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.13
	GFOL4.ud _z oh2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.80
	GFOL4.etheta _x	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
		1	3	5	7
		Eigenvalues			

Figure 32: Participation factors of the critical eigenvalues in PLL case.

the stability.

Figure 33: Eigenvalues changing voltage droop gain.

From the results, it can be concluded that the system could be unstable with big values of the droop gain. The participation factors of the critical eigenvalues are shown in Figure 34.

The participation factors show that these unstable eigenvalues are heavily related to the outer loop of the VSC in bus 18 and that a small interaction also appears with the VSC in bus 33.

Finally, the delay of the zero-order hold is modified. In this case, the results are shown in Figure 35. The participation factors of the unstable eigenvalues are plotted in Figure 36. Again, the participation factors are strongly related to the PLL, so when the delay is bigger in the measurements, the PLL synchronisation becomes worse, causing potential instabilities to the system.

3.7.2 Low SCR scenario

A case in which the SCR is lowered and compared to the original SCR=10 is studied, as Figure 37 shows.

If the SCR is lower than 8, with the current parameters, the system is unstable. The eigenvalues have more negative values if the SCR is increased. However, if the SCR decreases, a critical value is closer to instability. Figure 38 shows the participation factors of the unstable eigenvalues.

States	1	2
NET.iq ₁₂	0.15	0.15
NET.id ₁₂	0.18	0.18
NET.id ₁₃₄	0.20	0.20
GFOL1.q _{filt} _x	0.58	0.58
GFOL1.Ke _p	0.84	0.84
GFOL1.Ke _Q	1.00	1.00
GFOL1.cmdq ₂	0.71	0.71
GFOL1.is _q	0.18	0.18
GFOL1.is _d	0.21	0.21
GFOL1.ucap _q	0.47	0.47
GFOL1.ucap _d	0.52	0.52
GFOL4.q _{filt} _x	0.13	0.13
GFOL4.Ke _p	0.19	0.19
GFOL4.Ke _Q	0.23	0.23
GFOL4.cmdq ₂	0.16	0.16
GFOL4.ucap _q	0.11	0.11
GFOL4.ucap _d	0.12	0.12

Eigenvalues

Figure 34: Participation factors of the critical eigenvalues in voltage droop case.

Figure 35: Eigenvalues ZOH.

States	1	3	5	7
GFOL1.ud _m d	0.21	0.00	0.00	0.00
GFOL1.ud _z oh1	0.40	0.00	0.00	0.00
GFOL1.ud _z oh2	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
GFOL1.etheta _x	0.67	0.00	0.00	0.00
GFOL2.ud _m d	0.00	0.21	0.00	0.00
GFOL2.ud _z oh1	0.00	0.40	0.00	0.00
GFOL2.ud _z oh2	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00
GFOL2.etheta _x	0.00	0.67	0.00	0.00
GFOL3.ud _m d	0.00	0.00	0.21	0.00
GFOL3.ud _z oh1	0.00	0.00	0.40	0.00
GFOL3.ud _z oh2	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00
GFOL3.etheta _x	0.00	0.00	0.68	0.00
GFOL4.ud _m d	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.21
GFOL4.ud _z oh1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.40
GFOL4.ud _z oh2	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
GFOL4.etheta _x	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.68

Figure 36: Participation factors of the ZOH case.

Figure 37: Eigenvalues with different SCR.

States	1	2
NET.iq ₁₂	0.36	0.36
NET.id ₁₂	0.56	0.56
NET.iq ₁₄	0.61	0.61
GFOL1.Ke ₃	0.58	0.58
GFOL1.Ke _P	1.00	1.00
GFOL1.cmdq ₂	0.34	0.34
GFOL1.is	0.12	0.12
GFOL1.ucap _q	0.23	0.23
GFOL1.ucap _q	0.41	0.41
GFOL2.Ke _d	0.39	0.39
GFOL2.Ke _P	0.70	0.70
GFOL2.cmdq ₂	0.23	0.23
GFOL2.ucap _q	0.16	0.16
GFOL2.ucap _q	0.28	0.28
GFOL3.Ke _d	0.39	0.39
GFOL3.Ke _P	0.68	0.68
GFOL3.cmdq ₂	0.23	0.23
GFOL3.ucap _q	0.16	0.16
GFOL3.ucap _q	0.28	0.28
GFOL4.Ke _d	0.47	0.47
GFOL4.Ke _P	0.82	0.82
GFOL4.cmdq ₂	0.28	0.28
GFOL4.ucap _q	0.19	0.19
GFOL4.ucap _d	0.34	0.34

Figure 38: Participation factors with different SCRs.

The participation factors suggest that the outer loops of the converters and the grid are related to the instability. Hence the outer loops are changed with a SCR=2.

The results in Figure 39 show the effect that the active power outer loops have in the system when the SCR is low. Hence, stability could be ensured by lowering the time constants. On the other hand, the time constants of the outer loops have to accomplish the grid requirements. If the reactive power outer loop is varied, as shown in Figure 40, again the system could be stable with high values of the time constant of the reactive power outer loop.

Therefore, the stability of the system if the SCR is very low is highly related to the outer loops. Apart from that, the damping ratio is also related to these parameters. Consequently, dynamic variation is important.

3.7.3 Switches

In this section, the critical system eigenvalues are plotted varying the structure of the grid. To check the change of topology, 8 different scenarios have been studied, as shown in Table 4:

The obtained results are plotted in Figure 41.

The results show no significant correlation between poles. However, in the cases where line 2-19 is lost, the system is unstable. The participation factors of this case are shown in Figure 42.

Figure 39: Eigenvalues with different active power time constants and low SCR.

Figure 40: Eigenvalues with different reactive power time constants and low SCR.

Figure 41: Eigenvalues with different switches closed.

States	1	2
NET.iq ₁₂	0.22	0.22
NET.id ₁₂	0.17	0.17
NET.id ₁₃	0.21	0.21
NET.iq ₅₆	0.13	0.13
GFOL1.Ke _P	0.96	0.96
GFOL1.Ke _Q	1.00	1.00
GFOL1.cmdq ₂	0.78	0.78
GFOL1.is _q	0.18	0.18
GFOL1.is _d	0.21	0.21
GFOL1.ucap _q	0.51	0.51
GFOL1.ucap _d	0.56	0.56
GFOL2.Ke _P	0.24	0.24
GFOL2.Ke _Q	0.25	0.25
GFOL2.cmdq ₂	0.19	0.19
GFOL2.ucap _q	0.13	0.13
GFOL2.ucap _d	0.14	0.14
GFOL4.Ke _P	0.26	0.26
GFOL4.Ke _Q	0.27	0.27
GFOL4.cmdq ₂	0.21	0.21
GFOL4.ucap _q	0.14	0.14
GFOL4.ucap _d	0.16	0.16

Figure 42: Participation factors with line 2-19 lost.

Case	Lost	Switchable
1	None	None
2	None	25-29
3	None	8-21
4	None	12-22
5	None	All
6	3-23	25-29
7	2-19	8-21
8	2-19	12-22

Table 4: Lines and switchable lines relationship.

Participation factors show that the instability is again related to the outer loop of the converter which is at more distance from the main grid. Also, all the converters are affected by this instability but with different importance depending on the distance. Therefore, the addition of an MPC could be an option to increase the resiliency of the system.

3.7.4 GFOM/GFOL converters comparison

GFOR converters could ensure the stability of the grid with a feeder with low SCR. In this case, the main grid has a SCR of 0.5, and the converters in buses 18 and 22 are operating in GFOR mode. Therefore, the comparison with the eigenvalues obtained in the base case is shown in Figure 43.

Figure 43: Eigenvalues with grid-forming (1) and grid-following (2) modes in a low SCR grid.

As can be seen in the results, if half of the converters are in GFOR mode, the system

is stable. However, three eigenvalues without oscillation appear very close to the 0-axis line. If the participation factors of these eigenvalues are analysed, as shown in Figure 44 it can be seen that these eigenvalues are related to the grid-forming control. The eigenvalue closer to 0 is related to the calculated angle of the converter while the other two are related to the integral part of the voltage control.

States	GFOR1.etheta _x	0.00	0.00	0.49
	GFOR1.Ke _{uq}	0.26	0.50	0.00
	GFOR1.Ke _{ud}	0.50	0.26	0.00
	GFOR2.etheta _x	0.00	0.00	1.00
	GFOR2.Ke _{uq}	0.53	1.00	0.00
	GFOR2.Ke _{ud}	1.00	0.53	0.00
		58	61	62
		Eigenvalues		

Figure 44: Participation factors of the critical eigenvalues in GFOR mode.

3.7.5 MPC inclusion

If in the IEEE 33 bus system, the MPC is included, the non-linear and the linear models have to be validated again. The converter has been added between buses 8 and 21. Hence, a disturbance of 5% is applied in the load connected to bus 21. Some of the signals measured in both models are compared in Figure 45.

With the linear model validated, a small signal study is performed. A couple of poles with a damping factor near 0 appear close to the positive real axis. These eigenvalues are related to the DC line, however, in a real MPC a small cable exists between the ports, not a DC line. Therefore, as these poles are a result of how the MPC is modelled, they are not considered in the analysis. To check the changes in the dynamics due to the addition of the MPC, the eigenvalues of both linear models (base case and MPC case) are shown in the same map in Figure 46.

From the comparison, it can be seen that with the addition of the MPC, two eigenvalues have a real value bigger than 0. The participation factors of these eigenvalues are shown

Figure 45: DC voltage, current and AC power of the MPC in bus 21 with linear and non-linear models.

Figure 46: Eigenvalues in the base case (1) and MPC case (2).

in Figure 47.

States	1	2
NET.iq ₁₂	0.32	0.32
NET.id ₁₂	0.24	0.24
NET.iq ₁₃ ⁴	0.11	0.11
NET.id ₁₃ ⁴	0.30	0.30
NET.iq ₅₆	0.12	0.12
GFOL1.Ke _p	0.96	0.96
GFOL1.Ke _Q	1.00	1.00
GFOL1.cmdq ₂	0.77	0.77
GFOL1.is _q	0.18	0.18
GFOL1.is _d	0.20	0.20
GFOL1.ucap _q	0.51	0.51
GFOL1.ucap _d	0.56	0.56
GFOL4.Ke _p	0.28	0.28
GFOL4.Ke _Q	0.29	0.29
GFOL4.cmdq ₂	0.23	0.23
GFOL4.ucap _q	0.15	0.15
GFOL4.ucap _d	0.16	0.16
MPC1.Ke _p	0.20	0.20
MPC1.Ke _Q	0.20	0.20
MPC1.cmdq ₂	0.17	0.17
MPC1.ucap _q	0.10	0.10
MPC1.ucap _d	0.12	0.12

Eigenvalues

Figure 47: Participation factors with the MPC addition.

The participation factors show that as it happened in the base case, the eigenvalues strongly related to the outer loops of the VSCs are critical. Furthermore, the states of the outer loop of one MPC port and their filter voltages also participate. Therefore, the addition of the MPC produces a bigger interaction between ports that results in an unstable system.

From the results obtained in the previous sections, it has been concluded that a time constant of 0.2 s ensures that no poles have a damping ratio lower than 0.05. Therefore, the eigenvalues are studied again changing the outer loop time constant of all the VSCs and the MPC. The results are shown in Figure 48.

From the obtained eigenvalues it could be seen that in this case if the MPC is added the whole dynamics are expected (not undesired poles under the 0.05 damping ratio).

However, the VSC outer loops may be required to be 0.1 s. Therefore, if VSCs have an outer loop of 0.1 s fixed, a sensitivity analysis is done with the MPC changing both outer loops time constants. If the time constant of the active power is varied the results are shown in Figure 49.

When the time constant of the reactive power is changed the results are shown in Figure 50.

Figure 48: Eigenvalues in the MPC case with outer loop time constants of 0.2 s.

Figure 49: Eigenvalues in the MPC case with outer loop time constants of 0.1 s and changing the active power time constant of the MPC.

Figure 50: Eigenvalues in the MPC case with outer loop time constants of 0.1 s and changing the reactive power time constant of the MPC.

If we decide to change both time constants at the same time, which seems more realistic, the sensitivity analysis is such as shown in Figure 51.

Changing both outer loops time constants it is concluded that dynamics could be improved. With 0.5 s of time constant, the damping ratio is bigger than 0.05. The frequency of these eigenvalues is 28 Hz.

So, as a conclusion, the addition of the MPC in this case could improve the dynamics of the system, maintaining the original parameters in the VSCs.

Figure 51: Eigenvalues in the MPC case with outer loop time constants of 0.1 s and changing the active and reactive power time constant of the MPC.

4 Local controllers

This chapter illustrates the research outcomes of Task 4.2, related to the design of local controllers to ensure the reliable and stable operation of grid-connected MPCs. Taking advantage of the research described in deliverables D2.1 and D3.1, and based on the review and classification compiled D1.1, this chapter is structured as follows:

- The first section focuses on isolated MPCs and their controls, mainly the TAB. The section explores linear and non-linear control strategies and analyses the stability of MPC-based SOPs.
- The second section focuses on control of non-isolated MPCs, including their operation in abnormal conditions.
- The third section describes grid forming (GFM) controllers based on virtual oscillator control (VOC), that is a promising strategy for the control of MPCs, enabling the provision of grid services.

4.1 Small-signal stability analysis of an isolated MPC

To assess the stability of the controllers presented 3.2, the state space small-signal model of the isolated multiport converter is derived and a sensitivity study is performed. The model presented in Section 3.2 is used as a reference.

The models of each subsystem in the multiport converter are linearized using the small-signal approximation, and then the state space models are built. Once the state space matrixes of the subsystems are obtained, the matrixes are interconnected using the relationships between the inputs and outputs of each subsystem to obtain the multiport converter model. Hence, the system's eigenvalues are analyzed to study the impact of converter, controller, and grid parameters on the system's stability.

4.1.1 PLL small-signal model

Grid-following and some grid-forming control implementations require a grid synchronization mechanism. PLL is a popular and simple strategy to achieve such synchronization. The block diagram presented in Figure 11 is one common implementation and is considered for the small-signal model.

First, one must remember that the PLL aims to estimate the phase angle of the grid by measuring the voltage at the point of common coupling. Since the bandwidth of the PLL is limited, the real angle of the grid and the angle estimated by the PLL are equal only during steady-state (assuming zero error tracking). Therefore, there is an error during the transient. Thus, to study the dynamic stability of this subsystem, this angle error should be considered in the modeling. Figure 52 illustrates this.

The transformation matrix T_{pll} is derived from Figure 52 and is expressed in (29) assuming small disturbances in the phase angle. Hence, the grid measurements can be used in the dq control loops considering the PLL effect on it as in (30) and (31).

$$T_{pll} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\Delta\theta_{pll}) & \sin(\Delta\theta_{pll}) \\ -\sin(\Delta\theta_{pll}) & \cos(\Delta\theta_{pll}) \end{bmatrix} \approx \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \Delta\theta_{pll} \\ -\Delta\theta_{pll} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x^{d_{pll}} \\ x^{q_{pll}} \end{bmatrix} = T_{pll}(\Delta\theta_{pll}) \begin{bmatrix} x^{d_{grid}} \\ x^{q_{grid}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta x^{d_{pll}} \\ \Delta x^{q_{pll}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta x^{d_{grid}} + X^{q_{grid}} \Delta\theta_{pll} \\ \Delta x^{q_{grid}} - X^{d_{grid}} \Delta\theta_{pll} \end{bmatrix} \quad (31)$$

where x is a generic state (current or voltage), X is the steady state value of the generic state, and $\Delta\theta_{pll}$ is the angle difference between the real grid angle and its PLL estimation.

Considering the above equations, the state space small-signal model of the PLL is derived as follows.

Since the voltage at the PCC results from the grid and converter effects, the q – axis voltage at the PCC is expressed by applying the superposition principle as in (32). Furthermore, using (31), the PCC voltage measurement is transformed into the dq – PLL as in (32) and then filtered using a low pass filter as in (34). The filtered signal is input to

the PLL PI controller and the estimation of the frequency deviation is obtained as controller output, see (35). Finally the estimated grid angle is obtained in (36).

$$\Delta v_{pcc}^{q_{grid}} = \Delta v_g^{q_{grid}} \frac{L_{fg}}{L_{fg} + L_{grid}^{eq}} + \Delta v_{cf}^{q_{grid}} \frac{L_{grid}^{eq}}{L_{fg} + L_{grid}^{eq}} \quad (32)$$

$$\Delta v_{pcc}^{q_{pll}} = \Delta v_{pcc}^{q_{grid}} - V^{d_{grid}} \Delta \theta_{pll} \quad (33)$$

$$\Delta v_{pcc}^{q_{lpf}} = \Delta v_{pcc}^{q_{pll}} \frac{1}{1 + \tau_{pll} s} \quad (34)$$

$$\Delta \omega_{pll} = \Delta v_{pcc}^{q_{lpf}} k_p^{pll} + k_i^{pll} \int \Delta v_{pcc}^{q_{lpf}} dt \quad (35)$$

$$\Delta \theta_{pll} = \int \Delta \omega_{pll} dt = k_p^{pll} \int \Delta v_{pcc}^{q_{lpf}} dt + k_i^{pll} \int \int \Delta v_{pcc}^{q_{lpf}} dt \quad (36)$$

where L_{grid} is the grid equivalent inductance, the superscripts q_{grid} and q_{pll} refer to the q-axis of the grid and PLL synchronous reference frames, q_{lpf} indicate a filtered signal, k_p^{pll} and k_i^{pll} are the proportional and integral gains of the PI controller, respectively, τ_{pll} is the time constant of the low-pass filter, and $\Delta \omega_{pll}$ is the estimated angular frequency of the grid.

For the sake of easing the PLL state space model derivation, the following auxiliary variables Δx_{pll1} , Δx_{pll2} , and Δx_{pll3} are defined in (37) - (39).

$$\Delta x_{pll1} = \int \int \Delta v_{pcc}^{q_{lpf}} dt \quad (37)$$

$$\Delta x_{pll2} = \int \Delta v_{pcc}^{q_{lpf}} dt \quad (38)$$

$$\Delta x_{pll3} = \tau_{pll} \Delta v_{pcc}^{q_{lpf}} \quad (39)$$

From here, the dynamic equations are organized as in (40) to (42):

$$\frac{d\Delta x_{pll1}}{dt} = \Delta x_{pll2} \quad (40)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta x_{pll2}}{dt} = \Delta x_{pll3} \quad (41)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta x_{pll3}}{dt} = \Delta v_{pcc}^{q_{lpf}} - \frac{k_p^{pll} V^{d_{grid}} \Delta x_{pll2}}{\tau_{pll}} - \frac{k_i^{pll} V^{d_{grid}} \Delta x_{pll1}}{\tau_{pll}} - \frac{\Delta x_{pll3}}{\tau_{pll}} \quad (42)$$

Figure 52: PLL and PCC dq diagram.

4.1.2 Inverter small-signal model

Once the small-signal model of the PLL is obtained, the small-signal model of the inverter in dq is derived. The model is based on the linearization of (4) to (10) using the small-signal approximations. Equations (43) - (50) detail the inner and outer loop small-signal expressions.

$$\Delta v_{inv}^{dq*} = k_p^i (\Delta i_g^{dq*} - \Delta i_g^{dq}) + k_i^i \Delta x_i^{dq} \quad (43)$$

$$\Delta x_i^{dq} = \int (\Delta i_g^{dq*} - \Delta i_g^{dq}) dt \quad (44)$$

$$\Delta i_g^{d*} = (\Delta P^* - \Delta P) \left(k_p^P + \frac{k_i^P}{s} \right) \quad (45)$$

$$\Delta x_p = \int (\Delta P^* - \Delta P) dt \quad (46)$$

$$\Delta i_g^{q*} = (\Delta Q^* - \Delta Q) \left(k_p^Q + \frac{k_i^Q}{s} \right) \quad (47)$$

$$\Delta x_q = \int (\Delta Q^* - \Delta Q) dt \quad (48)$$

$$\Delta i_g^{d*} = (\Delta v_{dc}^* - \Delta v_{dc}) \left(k_p^{dc} + \frac{k_i^{dc}}{s} \right) \quad (49)$$

$$\Delta x_{dc} = \int (\Delta v_{dc}^* - \Delta v_{dc}) dt \quad (50)$$

where Δx_i^{dq} , Δx_p , Δx_q , and Δx_{dc} are auxiliary variables used to ease the state space model derivation.

Now, it is required that the dq current measurements are in the pll reference frame, thus, equations (43) - (44) are rewritten as follows.

$$\Delta v_{inv}^{d*} = k_p^i (\Delta i_g^{d*} - \Delta i_g^d - I_g^q \Delta \theta_{pll}) + k_i^i \Delta x_i^d \quad (51)$$

$$\Delta v_{inv}^{q*} = k_p^i (\Delta i_g^{q*} - \Delta i_g^q + I_g^d \Delta \theta_{pll}) + k_i^i \Delta x_i^q \quad (52)$$

$$\Delta x_i^d = \int (\Delta i_g^{d*} - \Delta i_g^d - I_g^q \Delta \theta_{pll}) dt \quad (53)$$

$$\Delta x_i^q = \int (\Delta i_g^{q*} - \Delta i_g^q + I_g^d \Delta \theta_{pll}) dt \quad (54)$$

Furthermore, the inverter modulation and processor delays are represented by a delay of $1.5\tau_s$, where τ_s is the sample period [13]. The delay is modeled as a first-order Padé approximation [14] and the resulting inverter voltage Δv_{inv}^{dq} can be defined as (55). Moreover, the dynamic of the Padé approximation is modeled as in (56).

$$\Delta v_{inv}^{dq} = \Delta v_{inv}^{dq} - \Delta v_{inv}^{dq*} \quad (55)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta v_{inv}^{dq}}{dt} = \frac{-4\Delta v_{inv}^{dq}}{3\tau_s} + \frac{-8\Delta v_{inv}^{dq*}}{3\tau_s} \quad (56)$$

Finally, the LCL small-signal model is obtained by substituting (55) in the differential equations that define the dynamics of Δi_{inv}^{dq} , Δi_g^{dq} , and Δv_f^{dq} as in (57) - (59). Moreover, the differential equations of the control states are presented in (60) - (64). Further expansion of the inverter differential equations system could be done by substituting $\Delta \theta_{pll}$, Δv_{inv}^{dq*} , and Δi_g^{dq*} in (57), (60), and (61). For simplicity, the complete equation is not written here.

$$\frac{d\Delta i_{inv}^{dq}}{dt} = \frac{\Delta v_{inv}^{dq} - \Delta v_{inv}^{dq*} - \Delta v_f^{dq} - \Delta i_{inv}^{dq} R_f}{L_f} + j\omega_n \Delta i_{inv}^{dq} \quad (57)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta i_g^{dq}}{dt} = \frac{\Delta v_f^{dq} - \Delta v_{pcc}^{dq} - \Delta i_g^{dq} R_{fg}}{L_{fg}} + j\omega_n \Delta i_g^{dq} \quad (58)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta v_f^{dq}}{dt} = \frac{\Delta i_{inv}^{dq} - \Delta i_g^{dq}}{C_f} + j\omega_n \Delta v_f^{dq} \quad (59)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta x_i^d}{dt} = \Delta i_g^{d*} - \Delta i_g^d - I_g^q \Delta \theta_{pll} \quad (60)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta x_i^q}{dt} = \Delta i_g^{q*} - \Delta i_g^q + I_g^d \Delta \theta_{pll} \quad (61)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta x_p}{dt} = \Delta P^* - \Delta P \quad (62)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta x_q}{dt} = \Delta Q^* - \Delta Q \quad (63)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta x_{dc}}{dt} = \Delta v_{dc}^* - \Delta v_{dc} \quad (64)$$

4.1.3 AC power calculations

The power injected into the grid can be calculated in the grid reference frame as in (65) and (66). Furthermore, the power measurements are filtered using low pass filters as shown in (67) and (68). The dynamic differential equations considered for the state space representation are derived from (67) and (68), and presented in (69) and (70).

$$\Delta P_{inv} = \frac{3}{2}(\Delta v_f^d I_g^d + \Delta i_g^d V_f^d + \Delta v_f^q I_g^q + \Delta i_g^q V_f^q) \quad (65)$$

$$\Delta Q_{inv} = \frac{3}{2}(-\Delta v_f^d I_g^q - \Delta i_g^q V_f^d + \Delta v_f^q I_g^d + \Delta i_g^d V_f^q) \quad (66)$$

$$\Delta P_{inv}^{lpf} = \Delta P_{inv} \frac{1}{1 + \tau_p s} \quad (67)$$

$$\Delta Q_{inv}^{lpf} = \Delta Q_{inv} \frac{1}{1 + \tau_q s} \quad (68)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta P_{inv}^{lpf}}{dt} = \frac{\Delta P_{inv}}{\tau_p} - \frac{\Delta P_{inv}^{lpf}}{\tau_p} \quad (69)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta Q_{inv}^{lpf}}{dt} = \frac{\Delta Q_{inv}}{\tau_q} - \frac{\Delta Q_{inv}^{lpf}}{\tau_q} \quad (70)$$

where τ_p and τ_q are the time constants of the low pass filters for the power measurements.

4.1.4 Isolated DC-DC

The isolated DC-DC stage in charge of the triple active bridge is modeled in (13) - (17). The small-signal is presented in (71) - (79). In (71), the phase-shift $\Delta d_{i,j}$ is the result of the control actions of the triple active bridge controller which regulates the voltages v_{dc2} as in (72) and (74). Δx_{dc2} and Δx_{dc3} are auxiliary variables introduced for the state space realization. Furthermore, $\Delta d_{2,3}$ can be obtained as in (76).

$$\Delta i_{i,j} = \Delta v_j \frac{N_{i,j} D_{i,j} (1 - |D_{i,j}|)}{2f_{sw} L_{i,j}} + \Delta d_{i,j} \frac{N_{i,j} V_j (1 - 2|D_{i,j}|)}{2f_{sw} L_{i,j}}, \forall i, j \in [1, 2, 3] \wedge i \neq j. \quad (71)$$

$$\Delta d_{1,2} = (\Delta v_{dc2}^* - \Delta v_{dc2}) \left(k_p^{tab2} + \frac{k_i^{tab2}}{s} \right) \quad (72)$$

$$\Delta x_{dc2} = \frac{\Delta v_{dc2}^* - \Delta v_{dc2}}{s} \quad (73)$$

$$\Delta d_{1,3} = (\Delta v_{dc3}^* - \Delta v_{dc3}) \left(k_p^{tab3} + \frac{k_i^{tab3}}{s} \right) \quad (74)$$

$$\Delta x_{dc3} = \frac{\Delta v_{dc3}^* - \Delta v_{dc3}}{s} \quad (75)$$

$$\Delta d_{2,3} = \Delta d_{1,3} - \Delta d_{1,2} \quad (76)$$

where V_{dci} and $D_{i,j}$ are the steady state values of the voltage at port i and phase-shift between ports i and j .

Finally, the differential equations used in the state space model are as follows:

$$\frac{d\Delta v_{dc1}}{dt} = \frac{\Delta i_1 - \Delta i_{1,2} - \Delta i_{1,3}}{C_1} \quad (77)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta v_{dc2}}{dt} = \frac{\Delta i_{1,2} - \Delta i_{2,3} - \Delta i_2}{C_2} \quad (78)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta v_{dc3}}{dt} = \frac{\Delta i_{1,3} + \Delta i_{2,3} - \Delta i_3}{C_3} \quad (79)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta x_{dc2}}{dt} = \Delta v_{dc2}^* - \Delta v_{dc2} \quad (80)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta x_{dc3}}{dt} = \Delta v_{dc3}^* - \Delta v_{dc3} \quad (81)$$

The currents Δi_1 and Δi_2 are currents flowing from the AC grids into the DC-links through the inverters, while Δi_3 is the current injected by the DC energy resource.

4.1.5 Stability and sensitivity analysis

With the models developed above, the eigenvalues of the system are analyzed. Furthermore, the impact of some parameters on the stability is assessed. The analysis is presented in subsections 4.1.6 to 4.1.9.

Figure 53: Eigenvalue sensitivity analysis for the proportional gain of the AC current controller.

4.1.6 AC current controllers

First, the impact of the AC current controller gains is assessed. The gains are designed the same for both d and q axis currents. The proportional gain has a greater impact on the stability of the converter than the integral gain. Therefore, a sensitivity of the proportional gain is considered for the analysis. Figure 53 reveals the impact of k_p^i on the stability of the converter. As the proportional gain increases, the poles move towards the right half-plane after an initial motion toward the left. The effect of the integral gain of this controller on the stability is not as significant. Thus, it is not explored in this report.

The effect of this controller on the system stability can be improved or worsened by the change of other parameters. For instance, When the grid inductance changes, the resonant frequency of the LCL filter is shifted, affecting the limits of the bandwidth of the AC current controller. This is explored in the following subsection.

4.1.7 Grid inductance and delays

Now, when the grid inductance increases, the “strength” of the grid is reduced, leading to stability issues, especially when PLLs are used to synchronize the inverter-based resources with the grid. Typically, an increase in the grid inductance will make the PLL more susceptible to grid disturbances. Furthermore, as the PLL uses the PCC voltage measurement, which is affected by both the grid and inverter voltages, a local loop is created, which could lead to instability. Figure 54 shows the behavior of the poles when L_{grid} increases.

Furthermore, the delays related to the set points calculations (A2D, DSP, etc) and the actuation of the converter, could affect the stability of the system. It is important to remark that a small delay is not always beneficial in terms of stability. This would depend on the

Figure 54: Eigenvalue sensitivity analysis for the grid inductance changes.

Figure 55: Eigenvalue sensitivity analysis for the PWM and DSP delay.

type of passive filter used to interconnect the converter to the grid. When the LCL filter is considered, a relatively small delay could jeopardize the stability if the current is measured in the grid side inductor and a minimum delay is required to guarantee stability. This is shown in Figure 55, where the delay modeled in (56) is added by increasing the sampling period τ_s . The opposite is true if the current is measured in the converter side inductor [13].

4.1.8 Power controller and grid services

The outer control loop in this case is related to the power controllers. Typically, the bandwidth of the outer loops is constrained by the inner loop controller. This is also true in this case, and increasing the proportional gain of the active power controller will lead the system to instability, as shown in Figure 56. Furthermore, when the outer loop includes

Figure 56: Eigenvalue sensitivity analysis for the proportional gain of the power controller.

grid-supportive control, its design also affects the system’s stability. In this case, a voltage droop control is included and the impact of the selected droop gain on the eigenvalue mapping is presented in Figure 57. Clearly, increasing the droop gain will make the system unstable. Furthermore, the bandwidth of the active power controller could improve or worsen the stability margins when evaluating different voltage droop gains. Figure 58 shows the same range of voltage droop gain as in Figure 57 but with a reduced power controller bandwidth. It is evident that the stability of the system is improved for changes in the voltage droop gain when the power controller bandwidth is reduced.

4.1.9 DC link control

The DC-link plays a major role in soft open-point solutions. In this case, there are three DC buses, one for each inverter and the third for the DC energy resource. Here, the eigenvalues for the multiport converter are first analyzed and a brief comparison is made between the multiport converter and two solutions for a two-port soft-open point.

The main parameter affecting the DC-link voltage stability is the control of the v_{dc} controller from the inverter. Since one inverter is controlled in Vdc-Q mode, it is constrained by the AC current controller bandwidth and the size of the capacitance. If the integral gain of the VDC controller is increased, the stability of the system will be endangered. Figure 59 shows how the eigenvalues are approaching the line marking the 5% damping as k_i^{vdc} is increasing.

Since there are several multiport converter topologies, it is interesting to compare the behavior of the eigenvalues for the back-to-back non-isolated soft-open point and the DC-isolated soft-open point based on the dual active bridge. Figure 60 shows how the impact

Figure 57: Eigenvalue sensitivity analysis for the voltage droop gain.

Figure 58: Eigenvalue sensitivity analysis for the voltage droop gain with reduced power control bandwidth.

Figure 59: Eigenvalue sensitivity analysis for integral gain of the DC link voltage controller.

of k_i^{vdc} is different for both soft-open point topologies. It is important to note that the state space of both topologies is very similar, and only two states are added in the case of the dual-active bridge. Also, the remainder of eigenvalues behave very similarly for both topologies.

Figure 60: Eigenvalue sensitivity analysis for integral gain of the DC link voltage controller. A comparison between B2B, DAB, and TAB.

4.2 Fault analysis of non-isolated MPCs

MPCs can facilitate the integration of new renewable energy power plants and technologies such as storage or electric vehicle chargers while keeping the grid quality and security and minimizing or avoiding critical conditions, that might compromise the continuous supply of

the users. The introduction of an MPC allows the implementation of many local actions, such as adding Energy Storage Systems (ESS) or connecting feeders, that improve the quality and stability of the grid along with optimization of the operation of the whole system. In addition, MPCs aim to reduce the total number of power electronics components or their total size, i.e. the total cost. The present section analyzes MPC’s contribution to increasing the resilience of DGs. A possible structure and control for an MPC is explained. Then, a case study is presented as an example to evaluate the operation of the grid during abnormal conditions when an MPC is introduced. This section presents multiple contingencies and shows how an appropriate MPC control can keep islands operating autonomously after severe disturbances occur. Dynamic simulations in Matlab/Simulink are used. The MPC analyzed in this section is a non-isolated 3-port structure with two AC-DC ports and one DC-DC port, as shown in Figure 61. The AC-DC ports are based on a two-level voltage source converter (2L-VSC).

Figure 61: Control structure of the 3-port non-isolated MPC

The ports are represented with average models i.e. without including the switching operation of the converters, which is enough to capture the dynamic response. On the AC side, the AC-DC ports are modelled with an LC filter and a three-phase controlled voltage source. Apart from that, the grid and the lines are modelled with RL circuits. On the DC side, the converter port is modelled as a current source. A capacitor is included in the common DC bus.

4.2.1 Converter Control

Both AC-DC ports have been defined as a master-slave control structure, therefore one port controls the DC voltage (V_{dc}^*) and the reactive power (Q^*), while the other port controls the

active power (P^*) and the reactive power (Q^*) [15]. The control structure used in both ports is a classical cascaded control with inner current control as defined in [16]. Moreover, ports could operate in grid-following (GFOL) or grid-forming (GFOR) modes. In the case of GFOL operation, both AC-DC ports operate with a Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) that synchronizes the converter with the grid. In the case of GFOR mode, a P-f droop is used to obtain the angle of the grid. Apart from that, with GFOR mode, a voltage loop is used to calculate the current references for the current control loops. It should be mentioned that the reference currents are saturated in both operation modes to ensure that the converter is always working inside the feasible physical limits. To ensure current support during faults, a Fault Current Injection block is used to introduce reactive current during the faults, as defined in [17]. AC-DC ports control is shown in Figure 62.

Figure 62: AC-DC control.

On the other hand, the DC-DC port has a cascaded control with an active power outer loop and an inner current control, as shown in Figure 63.

4.2.2 Validation of MPC operation in abnormal conditions

The abnormal operation of an LV distribution grid with an MPC is validated in this section. The studied system has two feeders connected to a common AC grid. Both feeders have been defined with different Short Circuit Ratios (SCR) to represent different distances from

Figure 63: DC-DC control.

the main AC grids. The feeders have loads connected to represent possible LV consumptions, as shown in Figure 64. Notice that the feeders have switches that could be opened when a fault exists. Therefore, AC-DC ports could be islanded. Faults are studied near the slave control port (p_2). If faults occur near the master control port, some modifications in the controllers are required.

Figure 64: Studied scenario.

To show the capabilities of MPCs, in the system under study an AC balanced fault is simulated between 2.8 s and 3 s. Apart from that, a battery connected to the DC part could be considered. The presented control design ensures that the DC voltage is controlled by the battery when available. Therefore, the following tests are presented:

- Test 1: AC balanced temporary fault with battery and switches closed during all the test.
- Test 2: AC balanced temporary fault without battery and switches closed during all the test.
- Test 3: AC balanced permanent fault without battery and switches S_{21} and S_{22} opened after the fault is detected.

AC-DC ports could operate in two modes: Grid-following (GFOL) or Grid-forming (GFOR). In the studied scenarios ports are always working on GFOL, except when a port is islanded,

in which case the port operates in GFOR mode. Therefore MPC ports' operation in Test 1 and 2 is summarized in Table 5.

Port	$t < 2.8s$	$2.8s < t < 3s$	$t > 3s$
p_1	GFOL	GFOL	GFOL
p_2	GFOL	GFOL	GFOL

Table 5: Test 1 and 2 AC-DC ports operation.

In the scenario studied in Test 3, the MPCs' ports operation is defined in Table 6.

Port	$t < 2.8s$	$2.8s < t < 3.05s$	$t > 3.05s$
p_1	GFOL	GFOL	GFOR
p_2	GFOL	GFOL	GFOL

Table 6: Test 2 AC-DC ports operation.

The parameters used are defined in Table 7. The equivalent impedance is calculated as:

$$Z_{eq} = \frac{U^2}{S_{cc}} \quad (82)$$

Where, $SCR = \frac{S_{cc}}{S_{c-N}}$. Therefore, the equivalent resistance R_{eq} and inductance L_{eq} are:

$$R_{eq} = \sqrt{\frac{Z_{eq}^2}{1 + \frac{1}{R/X^2}}}, L_{eq} = \frac{R_{eq}}{R/X \cdot 2\pi f_1} \quad (83)$$

The AC grid impedance is defined using a SCR of 10. In the feeders, the equivalent impedance varies depending on the SCR.

Parameter	Value
Nominal AC grid voltage, V_{ac-N}	400 V
Nominal port port power, S_{c-N}	300 kVA
Nominal DC bus voltage of MPC, V_{dc-N}	800 V
Short Circuit Ratio, SCR_1, SCR_2	10, 5
R/X ratio, R/X	12.25
AC-DC active power references, P_1^*, P_2^*	0.66 p.u., -0.66 p.u.
AC-DC reactive power references, Q_1^*, Q_2^*	0.33 p.u., -0.33 p.u.
DC voltage reference, V_{dc}^*	1 p.u.
DC-DC active power reference, P_3^*	-0.33 p.u.
Grid impedance, R_g, L_g	$0.7R_{eq1}, 0.7L_{eq1}$
Feeder 11 impedance, R_{11}, L_{11}	$0.15R_{eq1}, 0.15L_{eq1}$
Feeder 21 impedance, R_{21}, L_{21}	$0.15R_{eq2}, 0.15L_{eq2}$
Feeder 12 impedance, R_{12}, L_{12}	$0.15R_{eq1}, 0.15L_{eq1}$
Feeder 22 impedance, R_{22}, L_{22}	$0.15R_{eq2}, 0.15L_{eq2}$
Coupling impedance, R_l, L_l	0.01 p.u., 0.2 p.u.
Capacitor filter, C_f	0.15 p.u.

Table 7: Case study parameters

Test 1: Battery available and switches closed

In this first test, an AC balanced fault occurs between 2.8 s and 3 s. Additionally, the battery is connected during all the simulation. Switches are not opened in this case, however, due to the MPC, the DG is controlled during and after the fault. Notice that fault detection is represented by adding a delay of 10 ms.

Important events are defined in the results (Figures 65 and 66) as:

- 1: Fault starts (t=2.8 s).
- 2: Fault is detected (t=2.81 s).
- 3: Fault ends (t=3 s).
- 4: Fault end is detected (t=3.01 s).

Normal operation is ensured as results demonstrate that the converter perfectly follows its references. During faults, converter currents are saturated due to physical limits. Reactive current is prioritized because the battery maintains the DC voltage stable. The power of the battery varies to ensure DC voltage stability. Finally, it could be seen that the DC voltage does not have significant variations during the test, which is crucial as if the DC bus is not available, MPC could not exchange energy between ports.

Test 2: No battery and switches closed

In this second test, the scenario is as in Test 1 but without a battery, as it could be discharged or unavailable. Therefore, DC voltage is controlled by p_1 .

Normal operation is again guaranteed as converter signals are tracking their references. When a fault occurs and no battery is available, the master port (p_1) now prioritizes the active current to maintain the DC bus voltage stability. The other results show the same behaviour as with Test 1.

Test 3: No battery and switches opened after fault

In this third test, a balanced permanent fault starts at 2.8 s. When the fault occurs, S_{21} and S_{22} are opened with a delay of 100 ms. Therefore, port p_1 is islanded. Island mode detection time is 150 ms, as defined in [18]. Thus at 3.05 s, the control mode is changed to GFOR when the island mode is detected, as explained in Table 6. Once p_2 operates in island mode, the active power references are 0.

Important events are numbered to facilitate the understanding of the results:

- 1: Fault starts (t=2.8 s).
- 2: Fault is detected (t=2.81 s).
- 3: S_{21} and S_{22} are opened (t=2.9 s).
- 4: Operation mode in P_2 is changed to GFOR (t=3.05 s).

Figure 65: Test 1 results.

Figure 66: Test 2 results.

Figure 67: Test 3 results.

Results are shown in Figure 67. When the fault starts and is not islanded, p_1 still has voltage available. Therefore, active and reactive currents adapt their values to ensure the system's stability. On the other hand, p_2 voltage is 0 before the isolation of the fault. Due to the island operation and the GFOL operation, the voltage in p_2 is increased when the switches are opened until the mode of operation is changed to GFOR. Consequently, voltage has a transient until, thanks to the outer voltage control, it is stabilized to its nominal value. Currents are saturated, giving priority to the reactive current until the fault is isolated. When the fault occurs p_1 and p_2 active power references are 0. However, the active power measurements are 10 kW after the isolation, as ports change energy between them to ensure that the loads are fed. Reactive power in p_1 could follow its reference value after the opening of the switches. On the other hand, in p_2 the reactive power is -100 VAR to feed the isolated load. Additionally, DC voltage remains stable during all the simulation. Finally, when GFOR mode is activated, a transient appears due to the change of operation mode.

4.3 Unified Virtual Oscillator Controller

4.3.1 Introduction

Grid-forming (GFM) controllers are used to operate a voltage source converter (VSC) with a constant internal voltage-source. This operating objective enables GFMs to support and establish the voltage of electrical power systems [19]. This establishment enables GFMs to participate in functions such as islanded operation or the black-start of isolated network areas [20]. Additionally, GFMs are suited to operate on weak grids, where grid-following (GFL) controllers can struggle.

GFM control is valuable on distribution networks (DNs) as it may allow a multiport power converter (MPC) to connect to a remote/weak area of the network, can stabilise neighbouring GFL devices in the area [21], and can improve network resiliency by reducing the likelihood of outages or re-energising isolated areas.

However, the effective implementation of GFM MPCs faces several hurdles. The voltage-source nature of the GFM controller will drive an inherent current response to any changes on the grid. Although this is desirable for grid stabilisation, it makes the control of the current magnitude within the converter's strict thermal limits challenging.

Additionally, GFM strategies are often designed to operate in either reactive or resistive dominated networks. This is achieved by coupling active and reactive power with voltage angle and magnitude, or vice versa, to reflect the impedance characteristics of the network. However, medium voltage (MV) DN possess mid $X/R \approx 1$ ratios [22] where neither parameter can be neglected and there is increased coupling between the active and re-

active powers. Deliverable 2.1 explored the behaviour of a GFM Droop controller as X/R varies; showing the degradation in steady-state power transfer capability, the movement of controller poles and zeroes, and their relation to time-domain properties. Implementing a GFM strategy that is designed to operate in mid X/R conditions could offer improved stability and dynamics for the conditions that MV MPCs are expected to be implemented in.

Finally, the energy management strategy of a GFM MPC needs to be considered. The inherent response of GFM controllers to grid changes will demand power from the MPC, which needs to be managed to ensure power balance and stable operation of the device.

Conventional GFM controllers have been developed to emulate the voltage-establishing nature of synchronous machines (SM) with different levels of accuracy and detail. Virtual synchronous machines emulate the electro-mechanical dynamic equations of a SM [23], whereas, GFM Droop controllers simply emulate the primary control relationships [24]. This basis around a synchronous frequency is highly effective around the fundamental operating condition of the network but can be degraded as the operating point moves [25], which becomes more likely as more converters are connected. Additionally, conventional GFMs require time separation with respect to their cascaded controllers, which can be an issue in low switching-frequency (high power) devices, and whose design can introduce interactions on the network [26].

A different approach has explored the use of weakly non-linear limit cycle oscillator models to control VSCs. Due to the framing of the oscillator models in terms of a rotating voltage vector, they offer GFM voltage-source behaviour and have been shown to establish similar droop relationships on steady-state timescales [27].

Initial Virtual Oscillator Controllers (VOCs) emulated the dynamics of resonant RLC tanks to establish the VSC's internal voltage vector. Compared to conventional GFMs, which respond to averaged phasor power signals, the VOCs are shown to synchronise faster and more effectively further from the synchronous conditions. However, these initial proposals didn't fit with the physical limitations of VSCs and distributed energy resources (DERs), which possess strict thermal current limits and require dispatching to follow power references.

Advanced dispatchable and unified virtual oscillator controllers (dVOC and uVOC, respectively) were developed to overcome the hurdles of original VOCs. dVOC and uVOC use similar mathematical expressions including a fundamental oscillator dynamic, a synchronising feedback to control current delivery, and a voltage magnitude feedback.

dVOC and uVOC also both implement a rotational transform that aligns the control of active and reactive power with voltage angle and magnitude. The variable transform allows the choice of (or mixed) coupling of the powers and voltage components, which could improve the GFM's operation in the X/R conditions expected for the MPC application. How-

ever, few studies focus on the impact of the rotational transform on the VOC's operation and its relation to X/R conditions.

This chapter serves as an introduction to the principles of advanced VOCs and an initial overview of their features in X/R conditions. dVOC and uVOC have been shown to offer similar synchronisation, droop characteristics, and GFM/GFL mode switch ability. However, uVOC appears to be more suitable for current-limitation and fault ride through (FRT) due to its explicit arrangement in terms of current reference [28]. For this reason, uVOC will be analysed for the remainder of the chapter.

4.3.2 Control Overview

This chapter focuses on the operation of the GFM controllers in low X/R conditions. Accordingly, the control is tested on a simple power converter with ideal DC source connected via an LC filter to a Thevenin Equivalent representation of the grid, as pictured in Figure 68. The majority of the chapter focuses on uVOC, although some comparisons are made with the GFM Droop controller analysed in D2.1. The following subsections provide a brief overview of the GFM Droop control and a more detailed description of the uVOC control.

Figure 68: Single line diagram of example voltage source converter, electrical filters, and grid representation as used for Grid-forming Droop and unified Virtual Oscillator Controllers.

Droop controller Figure 69 pictures the GFM Droop control strategy. The controller uses 2^{nd} order Q-V and P-f droop relationships, due to the application of the controller in MV DNs where X/R is expected to be equal or greater than $X/R \geq 1$. A transient virtual impedance is used to shape the controller's response dynamics while a current-limiting virtual impedance acts to reduce the current magnitude above a threshold value I_{Thresh} . Cascaded voltage and current controllers are implemented to control the PCC voltage U and inductor current I_{cI} respectively to their prescribed references.

The base tuning of the GFM Droop controller is provided in Table 8, and more details can be found in D2.1.

Unified Virtual Oscillator Controller The uVOC (pictured in 70) emulates a weakly non-linear limit cycle oscillator using a Space Vector Oscillator model. The uVOC implements the state equations of the Space Vector Oscillator model internally, where the real and imaginary (α and $j\beta$) components of the internal voltage v are the states. The derivatives of the states describe the dynamic behaviour of the internal voltage: the imaginary β

Figure 69: GFM Droop control diagram.

Figure 70: uVOC control diagram.

component describes the rate of change of the voltage angle and the real α component describes the rate of change of the voltage magnitude.

The control can be considered in terms of three components: a fundamental harmonic oscillator generator, a synchronisation feedback to manage the current delivery, and an internal voltage magnitude feedback. The fundamental uVOC only requires the measurement of the output current to operate (however, grid voltage measurement is used to implement fault operation and recovery).

The fundamental harmonic oscillator (84) drives a synchronous limit cycle oscillation at $\omega = \omega_0$.

Table 8: Base GFM tuning and ideal VSC model parameters.

Parameter	Value		
General			
Nominal voltage	V_n	kV	20
Synchronous frequency	ω_0	Hz	50
Grid inductance	L_g	PU	0.33
Rated power	S_n	kVA	400
Filter resistance	R_f	PU	0.02
Filter inductance	L_f	PU	0.05
Filter capacitance	C_f	PU	0.05
Active power capacity	P_n	PU	0.7071
Reactive power capacity	Q_n	PU	0.7071
P-f droop coeff.	K_{pD}	PU	0.05
Q-V droop coeff.	K_{qD}	PU	0.05
Current threshold	I_{Thresh}	PU	1
GFM Droop			
Q-V droop time constant	τ_q	s	0.3
P-f droop time constant	τ_p	s	0.5
Voltage control proportional gain	K_{pVC}		0.0126
Voltage control integral gain	K_{iVC}		0.316
Current control bandwidth	ω_{CC}	Hz	100
Transient virtual inductance	L_{VZT}	PU	0.01
Transient virtual X/R	X/R_{VZT}		5
uVOC			
Virtual impedance time constant	τ_V	s	0.01
S-R current threshold	$I_{ThreshFRT}$	PU	1.1
S-R voltage threshold	V_{Thresh}	PU	0.95
X_r fall rate	$1/\tau_{FRT}$	s^{-1}	2
η_f integral time constant	τ_f	s	0.11
Over-current control bandwidth	ω_{OCL}	Hz	600

$$\dot{v} = j\omega_0 v \quad (84)$$

The action of η_f corresponds to the transition of the fundamental harmonic oscillator to a GFL uVOC. The internal voltage equation is updated to (85) to achieve synchronisation of the oscillator with the grid based on a current error e_i . The current error is defined relative to active and reactive power references according to (86).

$$\dot{v} = j\omega_0 v + e^{j\phi} \eta_f e_i = j\omega_0 v + e^{j\phi} \eta_f (e_{iP} + j e_{iQ}) \quad (85)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_{\alpha 0} \\ i_{\beta 0} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{NV_p^2} \begin{bmatrix} v_{\alpha} & v_{\beta} \\ v_{\beta} & -v_{\alpha} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} P^* \\ Q^* \end{bmatrix} \quad (86)$$

The active e_{iP} and reactive e_{iQ} current errors are aligned with the rate of change of voltage angle (imaginary) or magnitude (real) components using the rotational transform $e^{j\phi}$. ϕ can be used to account for the impedance characteristics of the connected network by setting $\phi = \text{atan}(X/R)$. When $\phi = \pi/2$ the change of magnitude is associated with the reactive current error e_{iQ} and the change of angle is associated with the active current error e_{iP} , similar to the P-f Q-V coupled GFM Droop controller. The P-f relationship exhibits a linear droop (but also depends on grid voltage U) (87) to oppose the fundamental synchronisation action of the oscillator, whereas the reactive current error is controlled to zero, emulating an integrator. Accordingly, the GFL uVOC is capable of synchronising with grid without the need for a phase-locked loop.

$$\omega = \omega_0 + \frac{\eta_f}{3U^2}(P^* - P) \quad (87)$$

The action of μ_f adds an additional voltage magnitude control term and transforms the GFL uVOC to GFM uVOC (88). While $\phi = \pi/2$ the linear voltage dependent $P - f$ droop is maintained but the integral Q-V action is augmented with a nonlinear Q-V droop relationship, as defined in (89).

$$\dot{v} = j\omega_0 v + e^{j\phi} \eta_f e_i + \mu_f (V_{p0}^2 - V_p^2) v = j\omega_0 v + e^{j\phi} \eta_f (e_{iP} + j e_{iQ}) + \mu_f (V_{p0}^2 - V_p^2) v \quad (88)$$

$$U^2 = U_0^2 + \frac{\eta_f}{6\mu_f U^2} (Q^* - Q) \quad (89)$$

When $\phi = 0$, suitable for a highly resistive network, the coupling is inverted so that the voltage magnitude exhibits a nonlinear droop with active power error and the voltage angle exhibits a linear but frequency-dependent droop with reactive power error.

uVOC Control Tuning The following subsection provides an overview of the approach used to tune the uVOC. A more detailed explanation of the derivation is provided in [29].

The tuning requires the definition of the maximum allowable voltage ΔV_{max} and frequency $\Delta \omega_{max}$ deviations. To enable the comparison with the GFM Droop controller in this chapter, the maximum deviations are defined relative to the corresponding droop coefficients (where the GFM Droop voltage relationship is defined in terms of peak L-L voltage but the uVOC voltage relationship is defined in terms of RMS L-N voltage).

$$\Delta \omega_{max} = K_{pD} * P_n \quad (90)$$

$$\Delta V_{max} = K_{qD} * Q_n / \sqrt{3} \quad (91)$$

The uVOC explicitly allocates fractions of its capacity to active P_n and reactive Q_n powers. The capacities are set equally to cumulatively contribute to nominal capacity.

$$P_n = Q_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} S_n \quad (92)$$

As mentioned above, the setting of ϕ determines the alignment of active and reactive power controls with voltage angle and magnitude. Accordingly, the tuning of the uVOC varies to reflect this coupling. For $\phi \geq \pi/2$, the control parameters η and μ can be tuned according to 93 and 94, respectively.

$$\eta = \frac{3\Delta\omega_{max}(V_0 + \Delta V_{max})^2}{P_n} \quad (93)$$

$$\mu = \frac{2\eta Q_n}{3((2(V_0 + \delta V_{max})^2 - V_0^2)^2 - V_0^4)} \quad (94)$$

When $\phi < \pi/2$, the control parameters are tuned according to

$$\eta = \frac{3\Delta\omega_{max}(V_0 + \Delta V_{max})^2}{Q_n} \quad (95)$$

$$\mu = \frac{2\eta P_n}{3((2(V_0 + \delta V_{max})^2 - V_0^2)^2 - V_0^4)} \quad (96)$$

Ancillary Controllers A low-pass filtered virtual resistor ($\frac{R_v}{\tau_v s + 1}$) is implemented during normal operation to improve the damping of the uVOC. Additional virtual impedance components can be included to support the harmonic performance of the uVOC during normal operation but are neglected for the purpose of this study.

A circular current limiter is implemented to scale the magnitude of the current when it exceeds the VSC's capability while maintaining its angle. The current limitation is achieved by comparing the magnitude of the unsaturated current reference $|i_o|$ with the threshold for current magnitude limitation I_{Thresh} . The proportional relationship σ is then used to scale the current's components.

$$\sigma = \frac{I_{Thresh}}{|i_o|} \quad (97)$$

The measured converter current magnitude $|i_c|$ is used to trigger fault condition signals X_f and X_r . The fundamental fault condition signal X_f is latched high using an S-R flip-flop when $|i_c|$ exceeds a threshold $I_{ThreshFRT}$, which must be larger than I_{Thresh} . The flip-flop is

latched low when the grid voltage recovers above a threshold V_{Thresh} . X_r is a complementary fault condition signal that is identical to X_f but is limited to fall at a slower rate τ_{FRT} to manage the return from faulted to normal conditions.

In the faulted condition (high latch) X_r is used to:

- Disengage the GFM voltage feedback controller and then use a variable $\mu_f = \mu(1 - X_r)$ tuning to support gradual fault recovery.
- Re-tune the current synchronising feedback controller $\eta_f = \eta(1 + X_r/\tau_f)$ with time constant τ_f and introduce a filtered virtual inductor $L_v = \frac{X_r L_v s}{\tau_v s + 1}$ to support the limitation of initial current transients.
- Engage an additional virtual resistor R_{OCL} to limit the current for the duration of the fault period. R_{OCL} is suggested to be tuned using (98) according to the worst expected fault conditions and desired current control bandwidth ω_{OCL} .

$$R_{OCL} = \omega_{OCL}(L_f + L_g) \quad (98)$$

4.3.3 Features of Unified Virtual Oscillator Controller

Critical features of the uVOC are introduced throughout the following section with reference to the MV MPC application and in some cases in comparison with the GFM Droop controller.

Global and Rapid Synchronisation VOCs were developed to provide a different VSC control approach that isn't constrained within a narrow margin around synchronous conditions; with the aim of faster dynamics and the ability to synchronise with a wide range of operating conditions. A comparison of GFM Droop and dVOC controllers showed that the dVOC could synchronise with a wide range of voltage frequencies, whereas the Droop was limited to synchronise around the synchronous frequency and with smaller phase differences [26]. This difference in synchronisation reflects the difference between the tested 1st order dVOC/uVOC and the 2nd order Droop controller, where similar differences were identified for 1st and 2nd order Droop controllers [30].

Similar analyses showed the improved synchronisation speed of VOCs when the allowable frequency deviation is wide but recognise that Droop controllers can synchronise faster when the allowable frequency deviation is narrow [31, 32]. While the benefits may be significant for microgrid or distant future converter-dominated networks, where operating conditions can vary significantly, the value should be considered for the MV MPC application, which may operate closer to the fundamental.

Several other features have been found to impact the synchronisation speed of VOCs. VOC response speeds are determined by tuning the synchronisation feedback controller but

must consider the degradation of the output harmonic content [25,29]. Additionally, the synchronisation speed is fastest when ϕ is set as either of $[0 \pi/2]$ (best fitting the grid X/R characteristics) [29]. Attention will need to be made regarding the uVOC’s synchronisation ability in mid X/R grids and if $\phi \neq [0 \pi/2]$. Finally, the rapid synchronisation of VOCs has been shown to destabilise systems composed of other slow moving plants e.g. SMs or conventional GFM controllers [33].

Steady-state Droop Characteristics Subsection 4.3.2 described the non-linear dependent droop laws experienced by uVOC. Figures 71 and 72 compare the measured uVOC and GFM Droop P-f and Q-V droop relationships, when the controllers use the tunings described in Table 8 and $\phi = \pi/2$. Both the uVOC and GFM Droop’s relationships are pictured for ideal configurations, where the current-limiting and FRT control actions are disabled.

Figure 71: $P - \omega$ droop relationship for uVOC and GFM Droop when $\phi = \pi/2$.

Figure 72: $Q - V$ droop relationship for uVOC and GFM Droop when $\phi = \pi/2$.

The first difference between the two droop relationships is the location of delivery, where the uVOC delivers its droop at its converter terminals (due to control action on converter current output), whereas, the GFM Droop delivers its droop at the PCC voltage U (due to its cascaded control action). Figures 71 and 72 picture the measured active and reactive power at these different locations for uVOC and GFM Droop.

Figure 71 highlights the voltage dependence of the uVOC P-f droop relationship, different to the linear independent GFM Droop relationship. Figure 72 exhibits the non-linear uVOC Q-V droop relationship, where the deviation from the linear GFM Droop relationship worsens as the voltage deviates further from the nominal value.

Figure 73: Active and reactive power reference tracking ability of the uVOC when $\phi = \pi/2$ and $X/R = 10$.

Power Tracking [33] suggests that the non-linear coupled power equations degrade the uVOC’s ability to control active and reactive power. This tracking ability is reproduced in Figure 73. The uVOC is shown to be able to track the active power reference accurately throughout large steps. In contrast, reactive power experiences deviations away from its reference as the active power varies and does not follow the reactive reference step. This behaviour is explored in [34], which uses the steady-state power flow equations of a resistive network. The conclusions can be extended for a reactive network using the corresponding power flow equations (99) and (100).

$$P = \frac{EV}{X_t} \sin(\delta) \tag{99}$$

$$Q = \frac{V^2}{X_t} - \frac{EV}{X_t} \cos(\delta) \tag{100}$$

In both cases, the frequency-linked power depends on the power angle difference δ , which can be derived as the integral of the frequency. Therefore, despite the P-f droop coefficient being a proportional gain, the angle is controlled with an integral gain. In contrast, the Q-V droop coefficient implements a direct proportional relationship between voltage

magnitude and its linked power.

Over-current and Faulted Conditions A key feature of the uVOC compared to other VOCs is its improved operation in over-current and faulted conditions. The following features are described as being critical for the uVOC’s management of over-current/faults:

- Internal GFL/GFM mode switch
 - GFL mode can be engaged by de-activating the voltage feedback control (setting $\mu_f = 0$). This is envisioned to enable prioritisation of current limitation during over-current conditions [35].
 - Alternatively, the engagement of GFM mode ($\mu_f > 0$) may be implemented if a VSC transitions from grid-connected to islanded modes. This can only be maintained as long as the uVOC remains within it’s current capacity.
- Ability to synchronise with an arbitrarily low grid voltage
- Fast over-current limitation
 - The uVOC is suggested to be more suited for fast over-current limitation compared to other VOCs due to its configuration in terms of a current error, which allows the direct application of the circular current limiter.

Figures 74 and 75 explore the uVOC’s FRT characteristics for a range of tunings, configurations, and grid conditions. The fault and converter conditions for each Figure’s PCC voltage and converter current pair are detailed in Table 9.

Table 9: Configuration, tuning, and operating condition of uVOC responses pictured in Figures 74 and 75.

Figure	Fault location	P^*	Q^*	R_v	L_v	R_{OCL}	$P^*(1 - X_r)$
74 a-b.	F_1	0.5	0	R_{v0}	L_{v0}	R_{OCL}	Off
74 c-d.	F_1	0.5	0	R_{v0}	0	R_{OCL}	Off
74 e-f.	F_1	0.5	0	$6R_{v0}$	L_{v0}	R_{OCL}	Off
74 g-h.	F_1	0.5	0	$6R_{v0}$	L_{v0}	R_{OCL}	On
75 a-b.	F_1	1	0.2	R_{v0}	L_{v0}	R_{OCL}	Off
75 c-d.	F_1	1	0.2	$6R_{v0}$	L_{v0}	R_{OCL}	Off
75 e-f.	F_1	1	0.2	R_{v0}	L_{v0}	R_{OCL}	On
75 g-h.	F_1	1	0.2	$6R_{v0}$	L_{v0}	R_{OCL}	On

Figure 74 exhibits the PCC voltage and converter current when a uVOC is subject to a distant 3 phase fault (location F_1) while the converter is operated at $P^* = 0.5 PU$, $Q^* = 0 PU$. 74 a-b. exhibits the response for the base configuration pictured in Figure 70 with tuning

in Table 8. The voltage sag occurs at $t = 0.1$ s. The GFM nature of the uVOC provides a large current injection until the current limiting action is engaged. The fault is cleared at $t = 0.2$ s, after which the converter experiences significant transients before converging on a stable operating point. This transient is not observed in [28], potentially due to the uVOC not being subject to such severe 3 phase faults but instead being subject to partial voltage sags.

Figure 74: PCC Voltage and Converter Current responses of the uVOC when subject to a fault at location F_1 with pre-fault conditions $P = 0.5$ PU, $Q = 0$ PU. The different tuning configurations of the subplot pairs are detailed in Table 9.

During the fault the converter experiences an initial transient current peak (to maintain pre-fault power and voltage levels) passing the current limiting threshold. This current peak briefly supports the PCC voltage before the current limiting action eventually scales the current magnitude back within allowable limits. The uVOC remains in fault mode for the remainder of the fault due to the low PCC voltage. As the current is scaled down towards 1 PU, it begins to ramp up before the fault is cleared in an attempt to track the power references. However, the power cannot be achieved and the current oscillates below its upper limit. Large transients are experienced following grid re-synchronisation.

Figure 74 c-d. exhibits the uVOC's performance when the virtual inductance is discon-

nected. The converter current continues to experience large transients at the onset of the fault, during its duration, and following grid re-synchronisation. PCC voltage experiences increased oscillations following grid re-synchronisation. However, the oscillations during the fault while the converter attempts to track the power references are reduced. This highlights the balance when implementing the (derivative-like) virtual inductor to support re-synchronisation while also risking the amplification of noise in the output.

Figure 74 e-f. exhibit the controller's performance when L_v is reconnected and R_v is scaled by six times. The large virtual resistor achieves more effective limitation of the fault current during the initial transient. However, the uVOC continues to over-actuate to track the power reference during faulted conditions and experiences significant transients during following fault clearance.

To mitigate this over-actuation of the controller a simple de-scaling of the active power reference is proposed, which uses the fault signal to de-activate and then gradually ramp-up the active power reference P_{FRT}^* during faulted and re-synchronisation conditions

$$P_{FRT}^* = P^*(1 - X_r) \quad (101)$$

The response of the uVOC with the de-scaled P_{FRT}^* is pictured in Figure 74 g-h. The over-actuation of the converter during the fault is completely removed, meaning that smaller voltage and current transients are only experienced during the initial fault and re-synchronisation events. This also minimises the impact of the virtual inductor noise amplification. Since the uVOC's over-current limiting resistor R_{OCL} is tuned for a worst case fault at location F_2 , the current is under-utilised during the fault at location F_1 . The slow re-synchronisation rate is determined by the ramp rate that X_r recovers with, in this case 2 s^{-1} .

Figure 75 a-b. and c-d. shows the original uVOC configuration in response to the same distant grid fault when the VSC operates at $P = 1 \text{ PU}$, $Q = 0.2 \text{ PU}$ with $R_v = [6R_{v0} \ 6R_{v0}]$, respectively. The controller exhibits similar performance as the equivalent configuration in the low OP; experiencing current transients at the fault onset (that reduce with larger R_v), over-actuation in the attempt to track the power references during the fault, and large transients during grid re-synchronisation.

Figure 75 e-f. and g-h. shows the proposed uVOC configuration in response to the same distant grid fault and operating point $P = 1 \text{ PU}$, $Q = 0.2 \text{ PU}$ with $R_v = [R_{v0} \ 6R_{v0}]$, respectively. The controller exhibits similar improvement; experiencing current transients at the fault onset (that reduce with larger R_v) but stable operation with prioritised reactive current delivery during the fault. The proposed configuration experiences worse PCC voltage dynamics during grid re-synchronisation.

Although tested, the response of the uVOC to a fault at location F_2 are not pictured as

Figure 75: PCC Voltage and Converter Current responses of the uVOC when subject to a fault at location F_1 with pre-fault conditions $P = 1 \text{ PU}$, $Q = 0.2 \text{ PU}$. The different tuning configurations of the subplot pairs are detailed in Table 9.

none of the tested configurations were capable of a stable response. The fault proximity pulls an exponentially growing fault current from the converter. The sustained current above the current limit suggests that more work needs to be done to enable safe operation in this worst case fault scenario. Future work will explore this phenomenon and explore the utilisation of cross-forming control adaptations, which may offer more robust current limitation and fault operation [36].

Inertial Response The uVOC is a first order GFM controller so does not inherently possess an inertial dynamic response. A parallel power increment is suggested to be added to enable the uVOC to provide inertial power injections [33], however, this moves the uVOC away from its fundamental objectives to provide global and fast synchronisation. Additionally, analysis has shown that an inertial dVOC experiences massive transients during active power reference steps and is highly sensitive to grid inductance [37]. Although the exact sensitivity of the first order uVOC to grid parameters should be explored in more detail, the inertial uVOC is not pursued further.

4.3.4 Impact of X/R

The uVOC has been analysed throughout this chapter (among other characteristics) to identify if it offers an improved control strategy to operate a part of the MPC in the expected low X/R conditions. Comparisons are made hereon to the analysis of the GFM Droop strategy in an identical system configuration and in terms of similar characteristics in D2.1.

Steady-state power transfer The following section will explore the steady state power transfer capability of the uVOC (with current limitation and FRT controls disengaged) as the active power reference is increased by 0.1 PU steps to 1 PU in different X/R conditions and as the configuration of the uVOC is varied.

Figure 76 pictures the active power transfer capability of the uVOC when $\phi = \pi/2$. The uVOC possesses the same inversion capability as was observed for the GFM Droop; supporting $P = P_n$ as low as $X/R = 0.15$. Also similar to the GFM Droop, the uVOC is less capable of rectifying $P = -P_n$ due to the asymmetry of the steady-state power transfer curve. Unlike the GFM Droop, however, the uVOC is incapable of rectifying 1 PU on grids with $X/R \leq 3.16$ due to the effective reduction of X/R by the large virtual resistance $R_v = 6R_{v0}$. Figure 76 shows that reducing R_v allows the uVOC to rectify rated active power as low as $X/R = 1.47$, which matches the steady-state transfer curve and the GFM Droop. Therefore, when choosing R_v , a balance needs to be made between over-current limitation and power transfer capability (particularly for rectification).

Figure 76: Steady-state active power transfer capability of the uVOC when $\phi = \pi/2$ for all of the tested X/R conditions.

Figure 77 exhibits the uVOC’s transfer capability when $\phi = \text{atan}(X/R)$ (assuming that the controller has knowledge of the grid impedance components or ratio). When $X/R < 1$, the controller tuning is switched to use (95) and (96), although this is identical to (93) and (94) in this case where $P_n = Q_n$.

Figure 77: Steady-state active power transfer capability of the uVOC when $\phi = \text{atan}(X/R)$.

Due to the definition away from $\phi = \pi/2$, and therefore away from the integral $P - \delta$ relationship, the uVOC no longer tracks the power reference. However, the tracking error improves as $\text{atan}(X/R) \rightarrow \pi/2$ (high X/R). The uVOC is stable while following all of the inversion and rectification set points for all of the tested X/R conditions as the low conditions no longer deliver large power.

Time-domain properties This section focuses on the active and reactive power dynamics during the final step in each of the above tracking examples.

All of the active power signals track from 0.9 PU to 1 PU when $\phi = \pi/2$ (Figure 78). In this case, the active and reactive power dynamics exhibit slowing of the rise time as X/R decreases, similar to that observed for the GFM Droop. However, the uVOC’s active power tracking exhibits a 1st order response, different to the non-linearity observed in the 2nd order GFM Droop, which was particularly severe in high X/R conditions.

Figure 79 focuses on the initial behaviour of the uVOC in response to the reference step, which highlights the minor and relatively consistent non-minimum phase zero (NMPZ) behaviour in the reactive power response for conditions where $X/R \geq 0.32$. This NMPZ behaviour is significantly less severe than that experienced by the GFM Droop in high X/R

Figure 78: Time domain properties of the uVOC in response to a power reference step from $P^* = 0.9 \text{ PU}$ to $P^* = 1 \text{ PU}$ when $\phi = \pi/2$ for all of the stable X/R conditions.

Figure 79: Zoom focus of the non-minimum phase zero behaviour of the responses pictured in Figure 78.

conditions.

When $\phi = \text{atan}(X/R)$ (Figure 80) each uVOC response is aligned to the same initial operating point at $t = 0 \text{ s}$. Again, the rise time of the active and reactive power responses slow as X/R reduce.

Minor NMPZ characteristics are observed in the reactive power response (Figure 81), which worsen slightly as X/R (and therefore ϕ) increase. The scale of the NMPZ behaviour remains much less severe compared to the GFM Droop.

Figure 80: Time domain properties of the uVOC in response to a power reference step from $P^* = 0.9 \text{ PU}$ to $P^* = 1 \text{ PU}$ when $\phi = \text{atan}(X/R)$.

Figure 81: Zoom focus of the non-minimum phase zero behaviour of the responses pictured in Figure 80.

5 System-wide coordination

This chapter aims at demonstrating the capability to coordinate MPCs from a system-wide perspective, in order to increase grid efficiency and reliability. The research outcomes described in the following sections focus on optimal grid operation and complement the results illustrated for MPC planning in Deliverable D1.2. The chapter is divided in two main sections:

- The first section describes the optimal dispatch of MPCs in power grids to minimize grid losses and voltage deviations. The problem, formulated as an optimal power flow,

returns the optimal P and Q setpoints for each MPC in the grid, given the selected objective function.

- The second section describes the utilization of model predictive control to coordinate MPCs connecting different energy assets, such as multiple microgrids. In this case, MPCs support the provision of grid frequency regulation services.

5.1 Optimal dispatch and coordination of MPC-based SOPs

This section presents the formulation of optimal power flow (OPF) problems aimed at determining the optimal operating points for each port in MPCs working as enhanced SOPs within a power grid.

The primary objective of the optimal scheduling strategy is to provide grid services such as voltage regulation and energy loss minimization. This is achieved by strategically setting the active and reactive power injections from the MPCs' ports. The optimal setpoints for these MPC-based SOPs are obtained by solving a non-linear optimization problem, considering the AC power flow equations, where the objective functions are tailored to the specific service requirements.

In this formulation, MPCs are represented using a power injection model that incorporates the device's technical constraints, making it suitable for optimal power flow analysis, without adding unnecessary modelling details.

The detailed formulation of the OPF problem involving MPCs is provided in (102) and further elaborated in this section. The objective functions (OF) considered will be described in 5.1.1.

A power grid with N buses is considered, where i and j are the indices of individual buses. In the general case, M_{MPC} MPC-based SOPs are included. The MPCs are modelled as virtual buses in the system, connected to two or more grid buses, resulting in a total of $N + M_{\text{MPC}}$ buses. Each MPC, denoted by m , is numbered progressively from $N + 1$ to N_{tot} , where $N_{\text{tot}} = N + M_{\text{MPC}}$. Furthermore, each MPC m has ρ ports, with ports identified by the index ρ .

$$\min_x \text{ OF} \quad (102a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } I_{ij} = \frac{|V_i| \angle \delta_i - |V_j| \angle \delta_j}{Z_{ij} \angle \theta_{ij}} \quad \forall i, j \in [1, \dots, N], i \neq j \quad (102b)$$

$$S_{ij} = |V_i| \angle \delta_i \cdot I_{ij}^* \quad \forall i, j \in [1, \dots, N], i \neq j \quad (102c)$$

$$P_{ij} = \Re(S_{ij}) = \frac{|V_i|^2}{Z_{ij}} \cos \theta_{ij} - \frac{|V_i| |V_j|}{Z_{ij}} \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j + \theta_{ij}) \quad \forall i, j \in [1, \dots, N], i \neq j \quad (102d)$$

$$Q_{ij} = \Im(S_{ij}) = \frac{|V_i|^2}{Z_{ij}} \sin \theta_{ij} - \frac{|V_i| |V_j|}{Z_{ij}} \sin(\delta_i - \delta_j + \theta_{ij}) \quad \forall i, j \in [1, \dots, N], i \neq j \quad (102e)$$

$$P_{G,i} - P_{L,i} - \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} P_{ij} = 0 \quad \forall i \in [1, \dots, N] \quad (102f)$$

$$Q_{G,i} - Q_{L,i} - \sum_{j \in \Omega_i} Q_{ij} = 0 \quad \forall i \in [1, \dots, N] \quad (102g)$$

$$P_{\text{MPC},m,\varrho} = \sum_{j \in \Omega_{m,\varrho}} P_{mj} \quad \forall m \in [N+1, \dots, N_{\text{tot}}], \varrho \in \Pi_{m,\text{lines}} \quad (102h)$$

$$Q_{\text{MPC},m,\varrho} = \sum_{j \in \Omega_{m,\varrho}} Q_{mj} \quad \forall m \in [N+1, \dots, N_{\text{tot}}], \varrho \in \Pi_{m,\text{lines}} \quad (102i)$$

$$-P_{\text{DER},m,\varrho} \leq P_{\text{MPC},m,\varrho} \leq P_{\text{DER},m,\varrho} \quad \forall m \in [1, \dots, M_{\text{MPC}}], \varrho \in \Pi_{m,\text{DER}} \quad (102j)$$

$$\sum_{\varrho}^{\rho} P_{\text{MPC},m,\varrho} = 0 \quad \forall m \in [1, \dots, M_{\text{MPC}}] \quad (102k)$$

$$|V_{\min}| \leq |V_i| \leq |V_{\max}| \quad \forall i \in [1, \dots, N] \quad (102l)$$

$$\delta_{\min} \leq \delta_i \leq \delta_{\max} \quad \forall i \in [1, \dots, N] \quad (102m)$$

$$P_{ij,\min} \leq P_{ij} \leq P_{ij,\max} \quad \forall i, j \in [1, \dots, N], i \neq j \quad (102n)$$

$$Q_{ij,\min} \leq Q_{ij} \leq Q_{ij,\max} \quad \forall i, j \in [1, \dots, N], i \neq j \quad (102o)$$

$$P_{\text{MPC},m,\varrho}^2 + Q_{\text{MPC},m,\varrho}^2 \leq S_{\text{MPC},m,\max}^2 \quad \forall m \in [1, \dots, M_{\text{MPC}}], \varrho \in [1, \dots, \rho] \quad (102p)$$

5.1.1 Objective functions

The objective functions (OFs) evaluated in this case study focus on minimizing voltage deviations and energy losses in the power grid.

Voltage regulation The objective of voltage regulation is to maintain the voltage magnitude $|V_i|$ at each bus within specified limits and to minimize deviations from the nominal value $|V_{\text{nom}}|$. This is achieved through the optimal operation of the MPCs in the grid. The

objective function can be expressed as (103).

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (|V_i| - |V_{\text{nom}}|)^2 \quad (103)$$

Losses minimization The objective of losses minimization is to reduce the overall energy losses in the grid. This is accomplished by optimizing the power flows through the MPCs, which in turn reduces the current in the most resistive lines. The objective function is defined as (104). The factor of 2 in the equation is included to avoid double-counting the contributions from each line.

$$\sum_{\substack{i,j \\ i \neq j}}^N \frac{|I_{ij}|^2 \cdot r_{ij}}{2} \quad (104)$$

5.1.2 Decision and state variables

The decision variables in this problem are the active power $P_{\text{MPC},m,\varrho}$ and reactive power $Q_{\text{MPC},m,\varrho}$ at each port ϱ of each MPC m . These variables determine how the MPCs inject power into the grid. The state variables, which describe the condition of the grid based on the chosen decision variables, are the voltage magnitude $|V_i|$ and the voltage angle δ_i at each bus i in the system.

5.1.3 Constraints

The following paragraphs outline the constraints defined in the OPF formulation.

Power flow equations The power flow equations describe the relationship between the electrical variables in the power grid under steady-state conditions. Eq. (102b) defines the relation between the current I_{ij} flowing from bus i to j as a phasor, where Z_{ij} and θ_{ij} are the magnitude and angle, respectively, of the impedance of the line connecting bus i and j . The conjugate of the current is employed to calculate the complex power in (102c), which is used to extract the active (102d) and reactive (102e) power.

Power balances The power balance constraints, represented by Eqs. (102f) and (102g) ensure that the sum of all incoming and outgoing power flows $P_{i,j}$ and $Q_{i,j}$ at each bus is balanced, accounting for generation and load, $P_{G,i}$ & $Q_{G,i}$ and $P_{L,i}$ & $Q_{L,i}$, respectively. Here Ω_i denotes the set of j buses connected to bus i .

Power balances at MPC ports The ports of MPCs can be connected either to power lines or to DERs that provide flexible demand and generation. Eqs. (102h) and (102i) apply to the set of ports $\Pi_{m,\text{lines}}$ of MPC m that are connected to power lines. These constraints

Figure 82: IEEE 33 bus system with a three-port MPC

ensure that the active and reactive power injected by each port equals the sum of the power flows on the lines connected to that port, where $\Omega_{m,\varrho}$ represents the set of buses j connected to the port ϱ of the MPC m . On the other hand, constraint (102j) applies to the set of ports $\Pi_{m,DER}$ of MPC m connected to DERs. The inequality represent the flexibility of the DER, that can adapt its power generation $P_{DER,m,\varrho}$ or consumption $P_{DER,m,\varrho}$ level depending on the need of the MPC. Non flexible loads can be modelled by replacing the inequalities with an equality constraint, which would represent a fixed level of generation or load.

MPC power balance The active power balance over all the ports of the MPC is guaranteed by (102k), while the reactive powers at each port are independent.

Technical limits constrains The final set of constraints (102l), (102m), (102n), (102o),(102p) enforce the technical limits of the system. These include constraints on voltage magnitudes, voltage angles, active and reactive power flows, and the sizing of the MPCs.

5.2 Case study: IEEE 33 bus system

In this case study, the IEEE 33 bus system is employed to demonstrate the application of MPC-based SOPs in power grids. The system's topology and load data are sourced from [38]. This grid is employed in the literature as a benchmark for distribution system studies. It is a radial grid consisting of four feeders of different length. In this setup, the ends of some feeders are connected via one or more three-port MPC-based SOPs, as shown in Figure 82, which are further connected to DERs through the third port, guaranteeing enhanced flexibility provision for the grid.

5.3 Base case: no MPCs

The power flow solution of the system without any MPCs serves as a benchmark to evaluate the impact of introducing MPCs between the feeders and their effectiveness in enhancing grid operations.

Figure 83: Graph representation of the power flow solution for the IEEE 33 bus system

The power flow solution is visualized in Figure 83, using a graph representation. In the figure, the size of the nodes corresponds to the voltage deviation at each bus, while the thickness and color of the edges represent the magnitude of power flowing through the corresponding lines.

Voltage deviations from the nominal voltage of 1 p.u. are the result of varying loading conditions within the network. Undervoltage typically occurs in overloaded networks, particularly in traditional grids without DERs, where it is most pronounced at the end of feeders, farthest from the power source. Conversely, overvoltage can be caused by an excess of generation, especially when DERs at the distribution level produce more power than the existing load can consume.

In the base case, as expected without distributed generation, the largest voltage deviations occur at the farthest buses of the longest feeders. The power flow results for this base case, illustrated in Figure 83 in terms of voltage magnitudes confirm this behaviour.

Regarding power flows, they are more pronounced near the source and gradually decrease along the feeders, as the loads at each node absorb a portion of the power. This affect grid energy losses, which are expected to decrease along the feeder, unlike voltage deviations.

The voltage profile of the grid is illustrated in Figure 84 (blue line). Considering voltage limits between [0.97, 1.03] p.u., the grid experiences undervoltages at different buses, specifically [10, ..., 18] and [28, ..., 33], with a minimum voltage reaching 0.949 p.u. .

The quality of the voltage profile over the grid is assessed using a voltage deviation index (VDI), defined as:

$$VDI = \sum_{i=1}^N |V_i - V_{nom}| \quad (105)$$

For the base case, the VDI is calculated to be 0.971. In terms of energy losses, the

Figure 84: Voltage profile of the IEEE 33 bus system with and without MPC between bus 18 and 33.

Table 10: P and Q setpoints of the MPC

	P [kW]	Q [kVAr]
Port 1 (18)	87	693
Port 2 (33)	- 145	1487
Port 3 (DER)	58	0

system experiences losses of 175 kWh under this operational scenario. These values will serve as benchmarks for evaluating the effectiveness of implementing MPCs in the grid.

5.4 MPC connecting bus 18 and 33

By analyzing voltage deviations throughout the grid’s feeders, the optimal initial placement for the MPC to enhance grid operation is identified between buses 18 and 33. The third port of the MPC is connected to a flexible asset capable of providing either power generation or demand, up to its maximum of $P_{DER,max} = 2$ MW. All ports are sized for a maximum of $S_{MPC,max} = 2$ MVA.

With an MPC positioned between buses 18 and 33, the voltage deviation across all nodes is significantly reduced, as illustrated in Figure 83. The minimum voltage rises to 0.993 p.u., which is closer to the nominal value than in the base case, and all bus voltages are maintained within acceptable limits.

In this scenario, the reduction in voltage deviation is primarily achieved through reactive power output from the multiport converter. The operational point of the MPC that results in these voltage improvements is detailed in Table 10, where positive values represent power output from the MPC and negative values indicate power input to the MPC.

Table 11: Results for voltage deviation minimization

MPC bus connections	V deviation index [p.u.]	Energy losses [kWh]
18, 22	0.474	207
18, 25	0.489	149
18, 33	0.300	171
22, 25	0.932	185
33, 22	0.493	147
33, 25	0.524	99

Table 12: Results for loss minimization

MPC bus connections	V deviation index [p.u.]	Energy losses [kWh]
18, 22	0.527	110
18, 25	0.554	88
18, 33	0.647	48
22, 25	0.950	141
33, 22	0.583	79
33, 25	0.610	61

5.5 MPC connecting different feeders

The MPC could be employed to connect different buses and their respective feeders, apart from buses 18 and 33. The assumption to be verified in this case study is that the position of the MPC greatly affects its capability to offer grid services. Furthermore, depending on the service provided, one position may be better than another. In this study, the positions are primarily limited to the ends of the feeders. Besides being optimal for managing voltage deviations, this placement also leads to a ring configuration that helps keeping loads energized in the event of faults in any of the feeders.

Both voltage deviations and energy losses are minimized for each position, and the results are reported in Tables 11 and 12, respectively.

Analyzing the tables provides several interesting insights. As expected, the best position for placing the MPC is between buses 18 and 33 for both voltage deviation minimization ($VDI = 0.300$ p.u.) and energy loss reduction ($E_{\text{loss}} = 48$ kWh).

It is also evident that a poorly placed MPC may not provide substantial improvements to the grid in terms of grid services. For example, placing an MPC between buses 22 and 25 results in only a slight reduction in both the VDI and energy losses compared to other positions.

The results also show that energy losses are influenced by changes in voltage deviation and vice versa. These objectives appear to be conflicting, although the extent of the trade-off depends on the MPC's position.

In the voltage deviation minimization scenario, energy losses can actually exceed the base case, with values such as $E_{\text{loss}} = 207$ kWh when the MPC is placed between buses 18

Figure 85: Energy losses for different cases

Figure 86: MPC connecting different feeders

and 22, and $E_{loss} = 185$ kWh when placed between buses 22 and 25. This is higher than the base case energy loss of $E_{loss} = 175$ kWh. Conversely, when energy losses are minimized, the resulting VDIs are consistently lower than in the base case, indicating that reducing energy losses inherently contributes to a more stable voltage profile. This is illustrated graphically in Figure 85, showing the energy losses for the different MPC locations and objective functions.

These findings demonstrate the importance of strategic MPC placement during the planning phase. The positioning of the MPC is critical for achieving specific operational goals.

In addition to the calculation of the VDIs, the voltage profiles for each MPC location are shown in Figure 86. The bad performance of the MPC in position (22, 25) can be verified by observing how the voltage profile in the corresponding case is almost identical to the base case. It is also worth highlighting that, although the presence of the MPC always improves the voltage deviations compared to the base case, some buses still remain slightly out of the lower voltage limit, excluding the case with the MPC between buses 18 and 33. This

Figure 87: Current flows and corresponding line resistances with the MPC connecting bus 18 and 33.

suggests that apart from positioning, better sizing of the MPC, with larger apparent power limits at each port in this case, may benefit grid operation.

Regarding energy losses, the MPC achieves minimization by adjusting power flows to reduce the current in lines with higher resistance. This is illustrated by comparing the graphs in Figure 87. Specifically, Figure 87a, shows the network with edges weighted according to the current flows, while Figure 87b presents the same network with edges weighted by the line resistances.

Emissions reduction The energy losses reduction obtained through the MPC can be translated into an equivalent greenhouse gas emission reduction. For example, considering the best case scenario, with the MPC located between bus 18 and 33 for the operational hour considered, the reduction in energy losses is equal to $\Delta E_{loss} = 175 - 48 = 127$ kWh. Considering an average emission factor of 273 gCO₂eq/kWh in Spain, for the year 2022 [39], the emissions avoided for this operational scenario are approximately 34 kg of CO₂eq, which are approximately 70% of the case without MPC. Assuming this value corresponds to the average emission reduction, the yearly emission reduction would sum up to 270 tons of CO₂eq reduction, in case the MPC would be employed for grid energy losses minimization. Of course, a more accurate evaluation of emission reduction requires considering marginal emission factors [40], the actual topology of a real grid, and different operational scenarios for different hours and seasons in a year. However, the 70% reduction obtained for this case study shows that the optimal operation of MPCs, correctly placed, sized, and operated, can lead to large amounts of emission reduction. Furthermore, MPCs can support the introduction of distributed renewable energy sources and reduce their energy generation curtailment, leading to additional emission reduction. Therefore, the expected emissions

Figure 88: P and Q setpoints of MPC ports for voltage deviations and losses minimization

reduction is likely to be of the same order of magnitude as that of the results presented here.

Operational points Another interesting aspect to consider is the variability of operational points in terms of P and Q setpoints of the MPC ports for each location and optimization objective. The operational points associated with the cases previously presented are illustrated in Figure 88, where orange operational points are associated with loss minimization and blue ones with voltage regulation. The figure highlights that the operational setpoints for loss minimization are mostly located in the first quadrant, regardless of the position of the MPC. Conversely, the P and Q setpoints associated with voltage deviation minimization depend strongly on the position of the MPC in the grid and are more scattered throughout the P - Q plane.

In conclusion, while positioning MPCs at the ends of feeders may be optimal for re-configuration and voltage regulation, this location might not always be the best choice for other objectives. For instance, when the objective of the MPC is minimizing losses, placing it MPC between buses 33 and 11, near highly resistive lines, can reduce energy losses to just 30 kWh.

5.6 Multiple MPCs

Multiple MPCs can be coordinated to achieve better performances in grid operation objectives. To evaluate the incremental benefit of adding more MPCs to the grid, an additional one is supposed to be installed into the IEEE 33 bus system.

Depending on the location of both MPCs, their ability to improve grid operation by minimizing energy losses or voltage deviation changes.

Figs. 89a and 89b show grid energy losses and voltage deviation indices for different

Figure 89: Energy losses and VDI when MPCs operate for voltage deviation minimization

combinations of MPC positions when the MPCs are operated to minimize grid losses.

The energy losses appear to be lower than the scenario with a single MPC, although the incremental benefit is not as significant as with the addition of a single MPC. The lowest losses, reduced to only 30.6 kWh, are obtained through the optimal coordination of an MPC connected between buses (18,33) and another between (33,25), with an improvement in losses of $\Delta E_{loss} \approx 18$ kWh with respect to the best operational point in the scenario with 1 MPC. However, from the voltage deviation perspective, the best operational point of 2 MPCs minimizing losses in the grid leads to worse voltage deviation indices than the scenario with 1 MPC, although still improving it compared to the base case.

The results for 2 MPCs optimally operating for voltage regulation are shown in Figure 90a and 90b, showing the energy losses and voltage deviation indices corresponding to the obtained operational setpoints. The best combination of MPC pair of locations appear to be (18,33) and (22,25), with $VDI = 0.2159$, further improving the operation of the grid with a single MPC in terms of voltage. It should be noted, however, that grid energy losses in this case are higher than the base case with almost all combinations of MPC positions, reaching more than double of the base case losses for the MPCs between buses (18,25) and (33,25). This tradeoff between voltage deviation and grid losses minimization should be taken into account by grid operators when setting the active and reactive power setpoints of MPCs operating as SOPs.

Finally, in both cases, the worst operating conditions are obtained when a port of an MPC is connected to bus 22.

The active and reactive power setpoints corresponding to the different position combinations of MPCs are plotted in the P-Q plane in Figure 91. The operational setpoints are considered for both voltage deviation and energy losses minimization.

Figure 90: Energy losses and VDI when MPCs operate for voltage deviation minimization

Similarly to the previous scenario with 1 MPC in Figure 88, optimal operation setpoints for energy losses minimization are mostly concentrated to the first quadrant of the P-Q plane, while the voltage regulation optimization leads to more scattered setpoints, depending on the location of the MPCs. This may be due grid losses minimization being a global problem, that improves in any case by injecting active and reactive power into the grid. On the other hand, voltage deviation minimization may require injection or absorption of either active or reactive power depending on the position of MPC. This result also shows that for the grid under study, assuming a uniform distribution of the loads over different time frames can safely expect a reduction of energy losses by injecting active and reactive power, without them being necessarily the optimal values. This is not true for voltage deviation, since setpoints in the wrong quadrant may worsen the operation of the grid in terms of voltage profiles, and specific values obtained through optimization are required.

Figure 91: P and Q setpoints of MPC ports for voltage deviations and losses minimization (2 MPCs scenario)

It is worth mentioning that the grid topology and physical values characterizing it in terms of resistance and reactance affect the capability of MPCs to be coordinated and provide grid services. For example, in case of the IEEE 33 bus system, the length of the feeders varies a lot, making it easier to spot the optimal location of MPCs for voltage deviation mitigation. Similarly, some lines have a much higher resistance than others, making it easier to optimize the system for energy losses minimization. This may not be the case for highly meshed grids, with similar resistances over different lines.

Finally, the present study considers a centralized optimization, with all the MPC involved contributing to the same objective function. This may not be the case when multiple MPCs have different, even conflicting, objectives. In that case, decentralized optimization should be employed to evaluate the optimal setpoints of all the MPCs.

5.7 DER integration

An additional scenario including the integration of PV plants in different buses of the IEEE 33 bus system is considered in this section, as shown in Figure 92. The aim is to evaluate the capability of MPCs to increase the grid's hosting capacity by mitigating overvoltages caused by the presence of distributed generation.

In this case, PV plants with a peak power of 800 kW in bus 20 and 200 kW in buses 6, 14 and 29 are considered. The resulting voltage profile shows overvoltage problems in buses 20, 21 and 22.

Figure 92: IEEE 33 bus system with MPC and RES integration

Similarly to the previous scenarios, the capability of the MPC to improve grid conditions is evaluated for different locations. The results are shown in Figure 93. Similarly to previous scenarios without DERs, an MPC placed between buses 18 and 33 leads to the lowest voltage deviation index. However, by looking at the voltage profile, it is clear that an MPC operating as SOP in that location cannot solve the overvoltage problems affecting buses 20, 21, 22. For this reason, it is important to check individual voltage levels in addition to the voltage deviation index when assessing the capability of an MPC to provide grid services through its optimal operation.

Figure 93: Voltage profile of IEEE 33 bus system in the presence of distributed generation, for different locations of the MPC

5.8 Model predictive control of MPCs

5.8.1 Objective

The objective is to develop a benchmark model predictive controller that operates independently of the specific power sources within the microgrid and can be seamlessly integrated into microgrids or hybrid systems. These systems may consist of various combinations of renewable and flexible power sources (e.g., PV+batteries, wind+H₂, BESS+H₂, renewable sources with flywheels, etc.), as illustrated in the conceptual diagram in Figure 94. It is important to emphasize that this conceptual scheme does not specify particular microgrid generators. However, it is assumed that the grid-connected AC output port of each microgrid is bidirectional, allowing it to both absorb and supply power to the grid. The same assumption applies to the input ports, where at least one is considered bidirectional, capable of both absorbing and generating power.

Figure 94: Concept of an N 'th grid-connected microgrid, dominated by a multiport converter (in green), with various possible DC-AC port configurations.

In power systems, when there is an imbalance between the demanded load and the generated power, frequency deviations occur. These deviations are typically mitigated to avoid reaching certain maximum limits that could cause irreparable damage to the power system. Various factors can lead to frequency imbalances, including generation or load

Figure 95: Frequency support control stages induced by a load disturbance. Δf denotes the frequency deviation and \mathcal{P}_d the amplitude of the load disturbance.

disturbances. In this study, we will focus on imbalances caused by load variations. The primary objective is to develop a controller capable of preventing and responding to frequency disturbances that may occur in the short term within the network to which the multiport converters are connected. The controller will mainly act in primary and secondary frequency responses, which are the fastest frequency responses, as illustrated in Figure 95. Note that the tertiary response will not be considered in this work.

In our case, the input power (which also considers the bi-directional ports) of each multi-port converter depends on the microgrid's capability to generate and absorb power, while the output power relies on the frequency deviations, Δf , observed by each microgrid interfaced with the multi-port converter. To define the power output at the inverter port of each multi-port converter, we consider the common ± 0.2 Hz maximum frequency deviation employed by most grid codes in Europe. This deviation is used to bound the required power for frequency restoration, \mathcal{P}_f , which is expressed in terms of the maximum and minimum power limits as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{P}_f = & -P_{\min} \cdot \theta(\Delta f - 0.2) \\
 & - \frac{\Delta f P_{\min}}{0.2} \cdot (\theta(\Delta f) - \theta(\Delta f - 0.2)) \\
 & - \frac{\Delta f P_{\max}}{0.2} \cdot (\theta(\Delta f + 0.2) - \theta(\Delta f)) \\
 & + P_{\max} \cdot \theta(-\Delta f - 0.2)
 \end{aligned} \tag{106}$$

where θ is the Heaviside function.

5.8.2 Methods

Model predictive control has shown promising results in the application of frequency support strategies, as demonstrated in [41, 42]. Model predictive control operates by predicting future system behavior over a defined time horizon and optimizing control actions based on these forecasts. When constraints are included, constrained predictive control becomes particularly advantageous for coordinating large systems. In the present case study, model predictive control serves as an effective tool for handling the real-time management of multiple microgrids interfaced by a multiport converter, accounting for system dynamics

and operational constraints.

There are several well-known architectures for model predictive control, including centralized, decentralized, and distributed approaches. The architectures and their benefits are discussed in detail by Scattolini [43]. In this work, we adopt a distributed model predictive control rather than a centralized control scheme, as it enhances scalability and is designed for a modular \mathcal{N} number of multiport interfaced microgrids. As the number of microgrids or converter ports increases, centralized control becomes computationally expensive and slower to react, whereas distributed model predictive control allows each local controller to make decisions based on local information, reducing the computational burden on a central entity. Additionally, distributed control offers greater robustness by mitigating single points of failure. If one part of the system fails, the remaining parts can continue operating, providing more reliable grid support.

In this work, we analyze the possibility of ensuring that the primary objective is met: enabling microgrids to collaborate in stabilizing grid frequency, a task that requires dynamic coordination of power flows while maintaining zero-load balance between the input and output ports of the multiport converter. Through constrained model predictive control, we aim to keep the system within safe operational limits—such as maintaining balance between power generation, consumption, and/or storage—while optimizing the frequency support provided to the main grid. This method is highly effective as it accounts for the inter-dependencies between microgrids and the grid-connected AC ports, predicting power demands and adjusting outputs to mitigate frequency deviations.

5.9 System modeling

The system modeling evolves around the concept introduced in Figure 94. Each microgrid or area interfaced by the multiport converters exhibits frequency dynamics, which can be described by the commonly used swing equation [44]:

$$\frac{d\Delta f}{dt} = \frac{1}{2H} (\Delta \mathcal{P}_m - \Delta \mathcal{P}_l - D\Delta f) \quad (107)$$

where H represents the system's inertia, capturing the resistance of the system to changes in frequency. $\Delta \mathcal{P}_m$ denotes the variation in supplied power, which includes the effects of frequency support requirements, such as those provided by primary control or fast-responding energy storage systems. $\Delta \mathcal{P}_l$ accounts for the controllable and uncontrollable power imbalances within the grid, which may arise from fluctuating loads or renewable energy sources. Lastly, D represents the damping coefficient, which models the frequency sensitivity of the load and helps to naturally stabilize frequency deviations.

For simplicity, in this study, we will analyze the simplest configuration, which consists

of three ports: two DC input ports and one AC output port. The AC output port connects to the local load of each microgrid as well as to the main grid connection of the area. The input ports are considered to represent a generator and an energy storage system, such as batteries, with the storage port being treated as bidirectional. This enables us to model the DC ports from the multiport converter in a unified manner [45], denoting the dynamics of the multiport $i \in N = \{1, \dots, \mathcal{N}\}$ interfacing each microgrid, and are described by the discrete-time invariant model

$$\delta_m \dot{x}(k+1) = -(\gamma_{mg}(k) + \eta_{in}^{-1} \gamma_{in}(k) - \eta_{out} \gamma_{out}(k)) \quad (108)$$

where γ_{mg} is a variable representing the demanded power of the microgrid, γ_{in} and η_{in} correspond to the power and efficiency of the input ports, respectively, and γ_{out} and η_{out} correspond to the power and efficiency of the output ports, respectively.

Let us establish that Φ_a is an element of the set of matrices $\mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ given by

$$\Phi_a = \{a_{ij} \in \mathbb{R} \mid a_{11} = 0.98, a_{12} = 0, a_{21} = 0, a_{22} = 0\} \quad (109)$$

and also define the matrix Φ_c as an element of the set of matrices $\mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$,

$$\Phi_c = \{b_{ij} \in \mathbb{R} \mid b_{11} = 0, b_{12} = 0, b_{21} = 0, b_{22} = 0.97\}, \quad (110)$$

to properly define the dynamics of δ_j , $\forall j \in \{1, 2\}$ as:

$$\delta_j(k+1) = \begin{pmatrix} \Phi_a & 0 \\ 0 & \Phi_b \end{pmatrix} \delta_j(k) + \begin{pmatrix} \phi_a & 0 \\ 0 & -\phi_b \end{pmatrix} \Delta x \cdot I(\gamma_{mp}), \quad (111)$$

being

$$I(\gamma_{mp}) = \theta(\gamma_{mp}) - \theta(-\gamma_{mp}), \quad (112)$$

where θ is again the Heaviside function, and γ_{mp} is defined as the balance between the input and output power at each multiport converter

$$\gamma_{mp} = \gamma_{in} - \gamma_{out}. \quad (113)$$

5.10 Model predictive controller derivation for frequency support

Figure 96 illustrates the implemented control diagram. On the left-hand side, the TSO (Transmission System Operator) sets a reference power based on the system's demand, which is directly linked to grid frequency deviations. This reference is sent to the predictive controller, denoted in the figure as DMPC. The controller uses this information, along with

Figure 96: Control diagram showing the interaction between the TSO, the DMPC predictive controller, and the multiport site control for managing microgrid power output and system feedback.

feedback from the plant's outputs, to send control signals to the local control layer of the multiport system managing each microgrid, referred to as the multiport site control. This control level adjusts the output power at the grid-connected AC output port based on the power levels at the input and output ports, as well as the local loads of each microgrid. Finally, the plant simulates the system's overall behavior and provides feedback to the predictive controller regarding the available power, input-output limits, and local loads, as shown in previous subsection.

The distributed model predictive control strategy aims to serve as a secondary layer for frequency support within each area managed by a multiport converter, and is formulated as the constrained multi-objective optimization problem:

$$\min_{x,u} \mathcal{J} = \min_{x,u} \sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{H}_p} \sum_{i=1}^N [\delta_1(i,k)^\top \mathcal{R} \delta_1(i,k) + \delta_2(i,k)^\top \mathcal{Q} \delta_2(i,k)] + \mathcal{S}_1 \alpha_P + \mathcal{S}_2 \beta_P \quad (114)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad (115)$$

$$x_j(k+1, i) = x_j(k, i) (1 - \mathcal{C}_{mg}^{-1}) + x^* \mathcal{C}_{mg}^{-1} + u(i) \xi_{mg}^{-1} \quad \forall j \in \{1, 2\} \quad (116)$$

$$\delta_1(k+1, i) = \Phi_a \delta_1(k, i) + \Phi_b ((x_1(k, i) - x^*(i)) \mathcal{C}_{mg}^{-1} + u_{\max}(i) \xi_{mg}^{-1}) \quad (117)$$

$$\delta_2(k+1, i) = \Phi_c \delta_2(k, i) + \Phi_d ((x^*(i) - x_2(k, i)) \mathcal{C}_{mg}^{-1} + u_{\min}(i) \xi_{mg}^{-1}) \quad (118)$$

$$x_j^{\min} \leq x_j(k, i) \leq x_j^{\max} \quad \forall j \in \{1, 2\} \quad (119)$$

$$u_{\max}(i) = P_{\text{up}}^* - \alpha_P \quad (120)$$

$$0 \leq u_{\max}(i) \leq \mathcal{M}_{\text{cap}}^{\text{in}} - P_{\text{load}}(i) \quad (121)$$

$$u_{\min}(i) = P_{\text{down}}^* - \beta_P \quad (122)$$

$$0 \leq u_{\min}(i) + P_{\text{load}}(i) \leq \mathcal{M}_{\text{cap}}^{\text{out}} \quad (123)$$

$$0 \leq \alpha_P \leq P_{\text{up}}^* \quad (124)$$

$$0 \leq \beta_P \leq P_{\text{down}}^* \quad (125)$$

where \mathcal{J} is formulated as a minimization problem, aimed at reducing the aggregated deviations in state variables δ_1 and δ_2 over a finite time horizon \mathcal{H}_p . This optimization considers their respective positive semi-definite weighting matrices \mathcal{R} , \mathcal{Q} , \mathcal{S}_1 and \mathcal{S}_2 . The inclusion of slack variables α_P and β_P allows the model to adaptively manage power imbalances and dynamic load conditions.

The state transition equations govern the evolution of each microgrid's states x_1 and x_2 at each time step k . They are functions of the sources' rate response in each microgrid to generate or absorb power \mathcal{C}_{mg} , and the total available capacity of the sources in the microgrid ξ_{mg} , while also incorporating the effects of the maximum and minimum control inputs u_{\max} and u_{\min} . The matrices Φ_a and Φ_c encapsulate the dynamic relationships within the system, determining how previous states influence future states. The constraints on state variables ensure that x_1 and x_2 remain within their respective operational bounds $[x_1^{\min}, x_1^{\max}]$ and $[x_2^{\min}, x_2^{\max}]$, respectively.

The control inputs are bounded above and below by $u_{\max}(i)$ and $u_{\min}(i)$, respectively, and are expressed in terms of the desired power levels P_{up}^* and P_{dw}^* , adjusted by the frequency slack variables to maintain system equilibrium. These inequalities are imposed on the control inputs to ensure operation within predefined limits.

Finally, the constraints on the control inputs reflect the physical limitations of the multiport converter based on the input port capacity $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cap}}^{\text{in}}$ and the output port capacity $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cap}}^{\text{out}}$, ensuring that the total generated power aligns with the load requirements without exceeding the capacity of the ports.

5.11 Cases for control validation

The following sections present various case studies to validate the effectiveness of the controller. This controller is based on the parameters outlined in Table 13, which have been validated for prediction horizons ranging from 10 to 20. To assess the accuracy of the controller, three distinct case studies will be introduced and detailed in the subsequent subsections. In all cases, the system is required to respond to a load of 0.02 per unit applied to the main area after 3 seconds of simulation.

Table 13: Main parameters and control settings utilized in the simulation.

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Value
Prediction Horizon	\mathcal{H}_p		10
Nominal frequency	f	Hz	50
Capacity multiport 1	\mathcal{C}_{mg}^1	kW	24
Capacity multiport 2	\mathcal{C}_{mg}^2	kW	32.4
Capacity multiport 3	\mathcal{C}_{mg}^3	kW	18
Capacity multiport 4	\mathcal{C}_{mg}^4	kW	12
Capacity multiport 5	\mathcal{C}_{mg}^5	kW	36
Load disturbance	$\Delta\mathcal{P}_l$	PU	0.02
Load disturbance time	$t_{\Delta\mathcal{P}_l}$	s	3

5.11.1 Available power in all multiports

Figure 97: Evolution of the controller’s response in providing frequency support. (a) System frequency evolution in response to a load disturbance, (b) Restoring frequency contributed by the combined multiport converters and the main area, and (c) Power distribution across individual multiport converters.

The first simulation case, presented in Figure 97 considers the availability of power across all multiport converters to provide frequency support. This implies that the power balance within the multiport converter of the microgrid is zero, and reserves are available to support the grid. The first figure illustrates the frequency evolution in the main area grid during a load disturbance. The second graph displays, in blue, the sum of the power from all multiport converters contributing to frequency support, while in orange, it shows the recovery of the main area with a much slower dynamics to achieve the power gain necessary for stabilizing the output to zero. The final figure depicts the behavior of the predictive controller’s decisions. In this system, no violations of constraints related to maximum or minimum limits occur; therefore, the predictive controller establishes the set points according to the generic equation that relates dynamics to the microgrid’s capacity. Since multiport converter 5 has the highest capacity, the green graph indicates that this system both generates and absorbs the most power among the five multiports. The controller’s response can be observed to be associated with the output capacities of the multiport converters.

5.11.2 Limited availability in some of the multiports

The second simulation case examines the unavailability of power in multiports two and four for participation in the system’s frequency stabilization. This occurs because the load in the microgrid connected to the multiport exceeds the power supplied by the two input

Figure 98: Evolution of the controller's response in providing frequency support, when multiports 2 and 4 cannot participate in the restoring. (a) System frequency evolution in response to a load disturbance, (b) Restoring frequency contributed by the combined multiport converters and the main area, and (c) Power distribution across individual multiport converters.

ports, resulting in the application of constraints (137) and (139). Consequently, the multiport controller is unable to deliver power to the main grid for frequency support in both multiports.

The first two graphs exhibit behavior similar to the previous case, but it is in the third figure where it becomes evident that the controller sets the output of the multiports without available power for frequency support to zero, while allowing participation from the multiports where the load is less than the available power at the input ports. In this scenario, multiports 1, 3, and 5 increase their power contributions, both generated and absorbed, to provide frequency support, with multiport 5 reaching output values close to 5 kW while absorbing approximately 4 kW at the bidirectional port. The remaining effects of the controller are similar to those observed in the previous case; since multiports 1 and 3 have lower capacity, their response magnitude is less significant compared to multiport 5, which has the highest capacity.

6 Conclusions

This report described the initial research outcomes of Work Package 4, mainly focused on the operation and control of distribution grids with MPCs.

The Deliverable was divided in three main chapters, one for each completed task of the work package so far.

In Chapter 3, two main use cases have been considered, one for the voltage analysis

of a real LV grid in Catalonia and another for the stability analysis of the IEEE 33 bus system. These use cases demonstrated that a stable and secure integration of MPCs into the network is possible, provided that certain design conditions are met, and control setpoints are correctly specified. Specifically, an MPC used as a SOP can significantly reduce the voltage deviations caused by the integration of RES in distribution grids. Furthermore. On the other hand, it was shown that MPCs can jeopardize power system stability, depending on the control strategy and the associated parameters.

Building on these results, Chapter 4 focused on the development of local control strategies for MPCs. The models developed in the previous chapters and Deliverables, specifically D2.1 and D3.1, have been employed to design and test PI controls, master-slave control for abnormal grid conditions, and virtual oscillator control. The small-signal models have allowed a sensitivity analysis of the impact that several controller and grid parameters could have on the MPC stability. Furthermore, the control strategies proposed guaranteed the exploration of MPC capabilities to support the grid under abnormal conditions by switching the control of the grid-connected inverter to grid forming during a fault, increasing the reliability of the grid. Also, the grid condition was deeply studied revealing the impact of X/R ratio on grid forming performance for distribution networks.

Finally, Chapter 5 describes centralized controllers for the optimal coordination of multiple MPCs, and the optimization of the setpoints of MPC ports, considering two main objective functions: voltage deviations and grid losses minimization.

It demonstrates that MPCs, when optimally coordinated, can significantly enhance grid operation, leading to a considerable reduction of grid losses and greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, their capability to improve voltage profiles in radial distribution grids makes MPCs a crucial asset to integrate more renewable energy sources while keeping the grid reliable.

Next, a model predictive controller was designed to coordinate multiple microgrids, each interfaced by multiport converters, in order to provide frequency support to a main area during load disturbances. The constraints for the multiport converters were defined based on the capacity of each microgrid and the allowable power limits of the input and output ports, ensuring effective primary frequency response until the slower control mechanisms of the main grid restore steady-state power. The use of distributed constrained model predictive controller offers an improved strategy for predicting disturbances and determining appropriate set points, considering the dynamic behaviors, capacities, and limitations of the multiport converters. This approach improves upon conventional methods such as droop control by leveraging predictive capabilities and optimizing system-wide performance.

In conclusion, the research outcomes presented in this deliverable, including the integration MPCs into the grid, advanced control strategies, and system coordination tech-

niques, lay a strong foundation for further exploration in the domain of grid-connected MPCs. These findings represent a critical first step toward the execution of Task 4.4 of the iPLUG project, which will focus on the experimental validation of grid-connected MPCs through Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) testing.

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